
SuPy Documentation

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Contents

1	Tutorials	3
2	Key IO Data Structures in SuPy	37
3	API reference	43
4	Version History	91

Caution: This site is under construction. Some information might NOT be accurate and are subject to rapid change.

- **What is SuPy?**

SuPy is a Python-enhanced urban climate model with [SUEWS](#) as its computation core.

The scientific rigour in SuPy results is thus gurranteed by SUEWS (see [SUEWS publications and Parameterisations and sub-models within SUEWS](#)).

Meanwhile, the data analysis ability of SuPy is greatly enhanced by [the Python-based SciPy Stack](#), notably [numpy](#) and [pandas](#).

- **How to get SuPy?**

SuPy is available on all major platforms (macOS, Windows, Linux) for Python 3.5+ via [PyPI](#):

```
python3 -m pip install supy --upgrade
```

- **How to use SuPy?**

- Please follow [Quickstart of SuPy](#) and *other tutorials*.
- Please see [API reference](#) for details.

- **How to contribute to SuPy?**

- Add your development via [Pull Request](#)
- Report issues via the [GitHub](#) page.
- Provide suggestions and feedback.

The following section was generated from `docs/source/tutorial/quick-start.ipynb`

1.1 Quickstart of SuPy

This quickstart demonstrates the essential and simplest workflow of `supy` in SUEWS simulation:

1. *load input files*
2. *run simulation*
3. *examine results*

More advanced use of `supy` are available in the *tutorials*

Before start, we need to load the following necessary packages.

```
In [1]: import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import supy as sp
import pandas as pd
import numpy as np
from pathlib import Path
get_ipython().run_line_magic('matplotlib', 'inline')

# produce high-quality figures, which can also be set as one of ['svg', 'pdf', 'retina', 'png']
# 'svg' produces high quality vector figures
%config InlineBackend.figure_format = 'svg'
```

1.1.1 Load input files

For existing SUEWS users:

First, a path to SUEWS `RunControl.nml` should be specified, which will direct `supy` to locate input files.

```
In [2]: path_runcontrol = Path('../sample_run') / 'RunControl.nml'
```

```
In [3]: df_state_init = sp.init_supy(path_runcontrol)
```

A sample `df_state_init` looks below (note that `.T` is used here to a nicer tableform view):

```
In [4]: df_state_init.filter(like='method').T
```

```
Out[4]: grid          98
        var          ind_dim
aerodynamicresistancemethod 0      2
evapmethod                  0      2
emissionsmethod            0      2
netradiationmethod         0      3
roughlenheatmethod         0      2
roughlenmommethod          0      2
smdmethod                  0      0
stabilitymethod            0      3
storageheatmethod          0      1
waterusemethod             0      0
```

Following the convention of SUEWS, `supy` loads meteorological forcing (met-forcing) files at the grid level.

```
In [5]: grid = df_state_init.index[0]
        df_forcing = sp.load_forcing_grid(path_runcontrol, grid)
```

For new users to SUEWS/SuPy:

To ease the input file preparation, a helper function `load_SampleData` is provided to get the sample input for SuPy simulations

```
In [6]: df_state_init, df_forcing = sp.load_SampleData()
```

Overview of SuPy input

`df_state_init`

`df_state_init` includes model Initial state consisting of:

- surface characteristics (e.g., albedo, emissivity, land cover fractions, etc.; full details refer to [SUEWS documentation](#))
- model configurations (e.g., stability; full details refer to [SUEWS documentation](#))

Detailed description of variables in `df_state_init` refers to [SuPy input](#)

Surface land cover fraction information in the sample input dataset:

```
In [30]: df_state_init.loc[:, ['bldgh', 'evetreeh', 'dectreeh']]
```

```
Out[30]: var      bldgh  dectreeh  evetreeh
         ind_dim    0          0          0
         grid
         98      22.0    13.1    13.1
```

```
In [7]: df_state_init.filter(like='sfr')
```

```
Out[7]: var      sfr
         ind_dim  (0,)  (1,)  (2,)  (3,)  (4,)  (5,)  (6,)
         grid
         98      0.43  0.38  0.001  0.019  0.029  0.001  0.14
```

df_forcing

df_forcing includes meteorological and other external forcing information.

Detailed description of variables in df_forcing refers to [SuPy input](#).

Below is an overview of forcing variables of the sample data set used in the following simulations.

```
In [28]: list_var_forcing = [
        'kdown',
        'Tair',
        'RH',
        'pres',
        'U',
        'rain',
    ]
    dict_var_label = {
        'kdown': 'Incoming Solar\n Radiation ( $\mathrm{W \ m^{-2}}$ )',
        'Tair': 'Air Temperature ( $^{\circ}\mathrm{C}$ )',
        'RH': r'Relative Humidity (%)',
        'pres': 'Air Pressure (hPa)',
        'rain': 'Rainfall (mm)',
        'U': 'Wind Speed ( $\mathrm{m \ s^{-1}}$ )'
    }
    df_plot_forcing_x = df_forcing.loc[:, list_var_forcing].copy().shift(
        -1).dropna(how='any')
    df_plot_forcing = df_plot_forcing_x.resample('1h').mean()
    df_plot_forcing['rain'] = df_plot_forcing_x['rain'].resample('1h').sum()

    axes = df_plot_forcing.plot(
        subplots=True,
        figsize=(8, 12),
        legend=False,
    )
    fig = axes[0].figure
    fig.tight_layout()
    fig.autofmt_xdate(bottom=0.2, rotation=0, ha='center')
    for ax, var in zip(axes, list_var_forcing):
        ax.set_ylabel(dict_var_label[var])
```

1.1.2 Run simulations

Once met-forcing (via df_forcing) and initial conditions (via df_state_init) are loaded in, we call sp.run_supy to conduct a SUEWS simulation, which will return two pandas DataFrames: df_output and df_state.

```
In [9]: df_output, df_state_final = sp.run_supy(df_forcing, df_state_init)
```

df_output

df_output is an ensemble output collection of major SUEWS output groups, including:

- SUEWS: the essential SUEWS output variables
- DailyState: variables of daily state information
- snow: snow output variables (effective when snowuse = 1 set in df_state_init)

Detailed description of variables in `df_output` refers to [SuPy output](#)

```
In [10]: df_output.columns.levels[0]
```

```
Out[10]: Index(['SUEWS', 'snow', 'DailyState'], dtype='object', name='group')
```

`df_state_final`

`df_state_final` is a DataFrame for holding:

1. all model states if `save_state` is set to `True` when calling `sp.run_supy` and `supy` may run significantly slower for a large simulation;
2. or, only the final state if `save_state` is set to `False` (the default setting) in which mode `supy` has a similar performance as the standalone compiled SUEWS executable.

Entries in `df_state_final` have the same data structure as `df_state_init` and can thus be used for other SUEWS simulations starting at the timestamp as in `df_state_final`.

Detailed description of variables in `df_state_final` refers to [SuPy output](#)

```
In [11]: df_state_final.T.head()
```

```
Out[11]: grid                                98
datetime          2012-01-01 00:05:00  2013-01-01 00:05:00
var              ind_dim
aerodynamicresistancemethod  0                2.0                2.0
ah_min              (0,)                15.0                15.0
                   (1,)                15.0                15.0
ah_slope_cooling    (0,)                2.7                 2.7
                   (1,)                2.7                 2.7
```

1.1.3 Examine results

Thanks to the functionality inherited from `pandas` and other packages under the [PyData](#) stack, compared with the standard SUEWS simulation workflow, `supy` enables more convenient examination of SUEWS results by statistics calculation, resampling, plotting (and many more).

Output structure

`df_output` is organised with `MultiIndex (grid,timestamp)` and `(group,variable)` as index and columns, respectively.

```
In [12]: df_output.head()
```

```
Out[12]: group              SUEWS
var              Kdown      Kup      Ldown      Lup \
grid datetime
98  2012-01-01 00:05:00  0.153333  0.018279  344.310184  371.986259
    2012-01-01 00:10:00  0.153333  0.018279  344.310184  371.986259
    2012-01-01 00:15:00  0.153333  0.018279  344.310184  371.986259
    2012-01-01 00:20:00  0.153333  0.018279  344.310184  371.986259
    2012-01-01 00:25:00  0.153333  0.018279  344.310184  371.986259

group              Tsurf      QN      QF      QS \
var
grid datetime
98  2012-01-01 00:05:00  11.775615 -27.541021  40.574001 -46.53243
    2012-01-01 00:10:00  11.775615 -27.541021  39.724283 -46.53243
```

```

2012-01-01 00:15:00 11.775615 -27.541021 38.874566 -46.53243
2012-01-01 00:20:00 11.775615 -27.541021 38.024849 -46.53243
2012-01-01 00:25:00 11.775615 -27.541021 37.175131 -46.53243

group
var          QH          QE ... DailyState \
grid datetime
98 2012-01-01 00:05:00 62.420064 3.576493 ...      NaN
   2012-01-01 00:10:00 61.654096 3.492744 ...      NaN
   2012-01-01 00:15:00 60.885968 3.411154 ...      NaN
   2012-01-01 00:20:00 60.115745 3.331660 ...      NaN
   2012-01-01 00:25:00 59.343488 3.254200 ...      NaN

group
var          DensSnow_Bldgs DensSnow_EveTr DensSnow_DecTr \
grid datetime
98 2012-01-01 00:05:00          NaN          NaN          NaN
   2012-01-01 00:10:00          NaN          NaN          NaN
   2012-01-01 00:15:00          NaN          NaN          NaN
   2012-01-01 00:20:00          NaN          NaN          NaN
   2012-01-01 00:25:00          NaN          NaN          NaN

group
var          DensSnow_Grass DensSnow_BSoil DensSnow_Water a1 a2 \
grid datetime
98 2012-01-01 00:05:00          NaN          NaN          NaN NaN NaN
   2012-01-01 00:10:00          NaN          NaN          NaN NaN NaN
   2012-01-01 00:15:00          NaN          NaN          NaN NaN NaN
   2012-01-01 00:20:00          NaN          NaN          NaN NaN NaN
   2012-01-01 00:25:00          NaN          NaN          NaN NaN NaN

group
var          a3
grid datetime
98 2012-01-01 00:05:00 NaN
   2012-01-01 00:10:00 NaN
   2012-01-01 00:15:00 NaN
   2012-01-01 00:20:00 NaN
   2012-01-01 00:25:00 NaN

```

[5 rows x 218 columns]

Here we demonstrate several typical scenarios for SUEWS results examination.

The essential SUEWS output collection is extracted as a separate variable for easier processing in the following sections. More [advanced slicing techniques](#) are available in [pandas documentation](#).

```
In [13]: df_output_suews = df_output['SUEWS']
```

Statistics Calculation

We can use `.describe()` method for a quick overview of the key surface energy balance budgets.

```
In [14]: df_output_suews.loc[:, ['QN', 'QS', 'QH', 'QE', 'QF']].describe()
```

```
Out [14]: var          QN          QS          QH          QE \
count  105408.000000  105408.000000  105408.000000  105408.000000
mean     42.574626     -2.128683     101.666596     22.880054
std     134.685026     83.616791     64.426005     28.535854
min     -84.389073    -81.747551    -44.370665    -0.649114
```

25%	-41.096052	-54.493597	52.976865	1.918672
50%	-24.869018	-43.957916	82.984095	13.057008
75%	77.405862	20.563903	140.933003	31.672138
max	689.067820	387.412149	338.167114	272.755143

var	QF
count	105408.000000
mean	79.047033
std	31.237533
min	26.333882
25%	50.066249
50%	82.896007
75%	104.858241
max	160.076122

Plotting

Basic example

Plotting is very straightforward via the `.plot` method bounded with `pandas.DataFrame`. Note the usage of `loc` for to slices of the output `DataFrame`.

```
In [15]: # a dict for better display variable names
dict_var_disp = {
    'QN': '$Q^*$',
    'QS': r'$\Delta Q_S$',
    'QE': '$Q_E$',
    'QH': '$Q_H$',
    'QF': '$Q_F$',
    'Kdown': r'$K_{\downarrow}$',
    'Kup': r'$K_{\uparrow}$',
    'Ldown': r'$L_{\downarrow}$',
    'Lup': r'$L_{\uparrow}$',
    'Rain': '$P$',
    'Irr': '$I$',
    'Evap': '$E$',
    'RO': '$R$',
    'TotCh': '$\Delta S$',
}
```

Quick look at the simulation results:

```
In [16]: ax_output = df_output_suews\
    .loc[grid]\
    .loc['2012 6 1':'2012 6 7',
        ['QN', 'QS', 'QE', 'QH', 'QF']]\
    .rename(columns=dict_var_disp)\
    .plot()
ax_output.set_xlabel('Date')
ax_output.set_ylabel('Flux ($ \mathrm{W \ m^{-2}}$)')
ax_output.legend()
```

```
Out[16]: <matplotlib.legend.Legend at 0x1263f4f98>
```

More examples

Below is a more complete example for examination of urban energy balance over the whole summer (June to August).

```
In [17]: # energy balance
ax_output = df_output_suews.loc[grid]\
    .loc['2012 6':'2012 8', ['QN', 'QS', 'QE', 'QH', 'QF']]\
    .rename(columns=dict_var_disp)\
    .plot(
        figsize=(10, 3),
        title='Surface Energy Balance',
    )
ax_output.set_xlabel('Date')
ax_output.set_ylabel('Flux ($ \mathrm{W \ m^{-2}}$)')
ax_output.legend()
```

```
Out[17]: <matplotlib.legend.Legend at 0x12642e8d0>
```

Resampling

The suggested runtime/simulation frequency of SUEWS is 300 s, which usually results a large output and may be over-weighted for storage and analysis. Also, you may feel apparent slowdown in producing the above figure as a large amount of data were used for the plotting. To slim down the result size for analysis and output, we can resample the default output very easily.

```
In [18]: rsmpl_1d = df_output_suews.loc[grid].resample('1d')
# daily mean values
df_1d_mean = rsmpl_1d.mean()
# daily sum values
df_1d_sum = rsmpl_1d.sum()
```

We can then re-examine the above energy balance at hourly scale and plotting will be significantly faster.

```
In [19]: # energy balance
ax_output = df_1d_mean\
    .loc[:, ['QN', 'QS', 'QE', 'QH', 'QF']]\
    .rename(columns=dict_var_disp)\
    .plot(
        figsize=(10, 3),
        title='Surface Energy Balance',
    )
ax_output.set_xlabel('Date')
ax_output.set_ylabel('Flux ($ \mathrm{W \ m^{-2}}$)')
ax_output.legend()
```

```
Out[19]: <matplotlib.legend.Legend at 0x126dccb70>
```

Then we use the hourly results for other analyses.

```
In [20]: # radiation balance
ax_output = df_1d_mean\
    .loc[:, ['QN', 'Kdown', 'Kup', 'Ldown', 'Lup']]\
    .rename(columns=dict_var_disp)\
    .plot(
        figsize=(10, 3),
        title='Radiation Balance',
    )
```

```
ax_output.set_xlabel('Date')
ax_output.set_ylabel('Flux ( $\text{W m}^{-2}$ )')
ax_output.legend()
```

Out[20]: <matplotlib.legend.Legend at 0x1272d6358>

```
In [21]: # water balance
ax_output = df_1d_sum\
    .loc[:, ['Rain', 'Irr', 'Evap', 'RO', 'TotCh']]\
    .rename(columns=dict_var_disp)\
    .plot(
        figsize=(10, 3),
        title='Surface Water Balance',
    )
ax_output.set_xlabel('Date')
ax_output.set_ylabel('Water amount (mm)')
ax_output.legend()
```

Out[21]: <matplotlib.legend.Legend at 0x127610668>

Get an overview of partitioning in energy and water balance at monthly scales:

```
In [22]: # get a monthly Resampler
df_plot=df_output_suews.loc[grid].copy()
df_plot.index=df_plot.index.set_names('Month')
rsmplM = df_plot\
    .shift(-1)\
    .dropna(how='all')\
    .resample('1M', kind='period')
# mean values
df_1M_mean = rsmplM.mean()
# sum values
df_1M_sum = rsmplM.sum()

In [23]: # month names
name_mon = [x.strftime('%b') for x in rsmplM.groups]
# create subplots showing two panels together
fig, axes = plt.subplots(2, 1, sharex=True)
# surface energy balance
df_1M_mean\
    .loc[:, ['QN', 'QS', 'QE', 'QH', 'QF']]\
    .rename(columns=dict_var_disp)\
    .plot(
        ax=axes[0], # specify the axis for plotting
        figsize=(10, 6), # specify figure size
        title='Surface Energy Balance',
        kind='bar',
    )
# surface water balance
df_1M_sum\
    .loc[:, ['Rain', 'Irr', 'Evap', 'RO', 'TotCh']]\
    .rename(columns=dict_var_disp)\
    .plot(
        ax=axes[1], # specify the axis for plotting
        title='Surface Water Balance',
        kind='bar'
    )
```

```
# annotations
axes[0].set_ylabel('Mean Flux ($ \mathrm{W \ m^{-2}}$)')
axes[0].legend()
axes[1].set_xlabel('Month')
axes[1].set_ylabel('Total Water Amount (mm)')
axes[1].xaxis.set_ticklabels(name_mon, rotation=0)
axes[1].legend()
```

```
Out[23]: <matplotlib.legend.Legend at 0x127add320>
```

Output

The resampled output can be outputted for a smaller file.

```
In [24]: df_ld_mean.to_csv(
        'suews_ld_mean.txt',
        sep='\t',
        float_format='%8.2f',
        na_rep=-999,
    )
```

For a justified format, we use the `to_string` for better format controlling and write the formatted string out to a file.

```
In [25]: str_out = df_ld_mean.to_string(
        float_format='%8.2f',
        na_rep='-999',
        justify='right',
    )
    with open('suews_sample.txt', 'w') as file_out:
        print(str_out, file=file_out)
```

End of doc/tutorial/quick-start.ipynb

The following section was generated from `docs/source/tutorial/impact-studies-parallel.ipynb`

1.2 Impact Studies Using SuPy in Parallel Mode

1.2.1 Aim

In this tutorial, we aim to perform sensitivity analysis using `supy` in a parallel mode to investigate the impacts on urban climate of

1. surface properties: the physical attributes of land covers (e.g., albedo, water holding capacity, etc.)
2. background climate: longterm meteorological conditions (e.g., air temperature, precipitation, etc.)

1.2.2 Prepare `supy` for the parallel mode

load `supy` and sample dataset

```
In [1]: from dask import delayed
        from dask import dataframe as dd
        import os
        import supy as sp
        import seaborn as sns
        import pandas as pd
        import numpy as np
        import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
        import matplotlib.dates as mdates
        from time import time

        get_ipython().run_line_magic('matplotlib', 'inline')
        # produce high-quality figures, which can also be set as one of ['svg', 'pdf', 'retina', 'png']
        # 'svg' produces high quality vector figures
        %config InlineBackend.figure_format = 'svg'
        print('version info:')
        print('supy:', sp.__version__)
        print('supy_driver:', sp.__version_driver__)

version info:
supy: 2019.2.8
supy_driver: 2018c5
```

```
In [2]: # load sample datasets
        df_state_init, df_forcing = sp.load_SampleData()
        # perform an example run to get output samples for later use
        df_output, df_state_final = sp.run_supy(df_forcing, df_state_init)
```

Parallel setup for `supy` using `dask`

In addition to the above packages, we also load `dask` to enable `supy` run in a parallel mode. Specifically, we will use `dask.dataframe` http://docs.dask.org/en/latest/dataframe.html`, a specialized dataframe extending pandas.DataFrame's ability in parallel operations, to implement a parallel supy for the impact studies in this tutorial.`

Given the nature of impact studies that requires multiple independent models with selected parameters/variables varying across the setups, such simulations well fall into the scope of so-called **embarrassingly parallel computation** that

is fully supported by `dask`. Also, as `supy` is readily built on the data structure `pandas.DataFrame`, we can fairly easily transfer it to the `dask` framework for parallel operations.

Internally, for a given forcing dataset `df_forcing`, `supy` loops over the grids in a `df_state_init` to conduct simulations. In this case, we can adapt the `df_state_init` to a `dask-ed` version to gain the parallel benefits through its parallelized `apply` method.

`dask.dataframe` essentially divides the work into pieces for parallel operations. As such, depending on the number of processors in your computer, it would be more efficient to set the partition number as the multipliers of CPU numbers.

```
In [5]: import platform
import psutil
list_info=['machine','system','mac_ver','processor']
for info in list_info:
    info_x=getattr(platform,info)()
    print(info,':',info_x)
cpu_count=psutil.cpu_count()
print('number of CPU processors:',cpu_count)
mem_size=psutil.virtual_memory().total/1024**3
print('memory size (GB):',mem_size)
```

```
machine : x86_64
system : Darwin
mac_ver : ('10.14.3', ('', '', ''), 'x86_64')
processor : i386
number of CPU processors: 12
memory size (GB): 32.0
```

To demonstrate the parallelization, we simply duplicate the contents in `df_state_init` to make it seemingly large. Note we intentionally choose 24 as the number for copies to accompany the power of CPU.

Before we move on to the parallel mode, we perform a simulation in the traditional serial way to see the baseline performance.

Baseline serial run

```
In [6]: # just run for 30 days
df_forcing_part = df_forcing.iloc[:288*30]
df_state_init_mgrids = df_state_init.copy()
# construct a multi-grid `df_state_init`
for i in range(24-1):
    df_state_init_mgrids = df_state_init_mgrids.append(
        df_state_init, ignore_index=True)
# perform a serial run
t0 = time()
xx = sp.run_supy(df_forcing_part, df_state_init_mgrids)
t1 = time()
t_ser = t1-t0
print(f'Execution time: {t_ser:.2f} s')
```

```
Execution time: 23.06 s
```

Parallel run

```
In [7]: # convert `pandas.DataFrame` to `dask.dataframe` to enable parallelization
dd_state_init = dd.from_pandas(
```

```

df_state_init_mgrids,
npartitions=os.cpu_count()*2)

# perform a parallel run using `map_partitions`
t0 = time()
xx_mp = dd_state_init\
    .map_partitions(
        lambda x: sp.run_supy(df_forcing_part, x)[0],
        meta=df_output)\
    .compute(scheduler='processes')
t1 = time()
t_par = t1-t0
print(f'Execution time: {t_par:.2f} s')

```

Execution time: 7.05 s

Check the data structure of xx_mp:

In [6]: xx_mp.head()

```

Out[6]: group
var          SUEWS
grid datetime Kdown      Kup      Ldown      Lup
0  2012-01-01 00:05:00  0.153333  0.018279  344.310184  371.986259
   2012-01-01 00:10:00  0.153333  0.018279  344.310184  371.986259
   2012-01-01 00:15:00  0.153333  0.018279  344.310184  371.986259
   2012-01-01 00:20:00  0.153333  0.018279  344.310184  371.986259
   2012-01-01 00:25:00  0.153333  0.018279  344.310184  371.986259

```

```

group
var          Tsurf      QN      QF      QS
grid datetime
0  2012-01-01 00:05:00  11.775615 -27.541021  40.574001 -46.53243
   2012-01-01 00:10:00  11.775615 -27.541021  39.724283 -46.53243
   2012-01-01 00:15:00  11.775615 -27.541021  38.874566 -46.53243
   2012-01-01 00:20:00  11.775615 -27.541021  38.024849 -46.53243
   2012-01-01 00:25:00  11.775615 -27.541021  37.175131 -46.53243

```

```

group
var          QH      QE      DailyState
grid datetime
0  2012-01-01 00:05:00  62.420064  3.576493  ...      NaN
   2012-01-01 00:10:00  61.654096  3.492744  ...      NaN
   2012-01-01 00:15:00  60.885968  3.411154  ...      NaN
   2012-01-01 00:20:00  60.115745  3.331660  ...      NaN
   2012-01-01 00:25:00  59.343488  3.254200  ...      NaN

```

```

group
var          DensSnow_Bldgs DensSnow_EveTr DensSnow_DecTr
grid datetime
0  2012-01-01 00:05:00      NaN      NaN      NaN
   2012-01-01 00:10:00      NaN      NaN      NaN
   2012-01-01 00:15:00      NaN      NaN      NaN
   2012-01-01 00:20:00      NaN      NaN      NaN
   2012-01-01 00:25:00      NaN      NaN      NaN

```

```

group
var          DensSnow_Grass DensSnow_BSoil DensSnow_Water  a1  a2
grid datetime
0  2012-01-01 00:05:00      NaN      NaN      NaN NaN NaN

```

```

2012-01-01 00:10:00      NaN      NaN      NaN NaN NaN
2012-01-01 00:15:00      NaN      NaN      NaN NaN NaN
2012-01-01 00:20:00      NaN      NaN      NaN NaN NaN
2012-01-01 00:25:00      NaN      NaN      NaN NaN NaN

```

```

group
var          a3
grid datetime
0  2012-01-01 00:05:00 NaN
   2012-01-01 00:10:00 NaN
   2012-01-01 00:15:00 NaN
   2012-01-01 00:20:00 NaN
   2012-01-01 00:25:00 NaN

```

[5 rows x 218 columns]

Perform a parallel run using `apply`:

```

In [8]: # perform a parallel run using `apply`
t0 = time()
xx_apply = dd_state_init\
    .apply(
        lambda x: sp.run_supy(df_forcing_part, x.to_frame().T)[0],
        axis=1,
        meta=df_output.iloc[0],
    )\
    .compute(scheduler='processes')
t1 = time()
t_par = t1 - t0
print(f'Execution time: {t_par:.2f} s')

```

Execution time: 9.98 s

Check the data structure of `xx_apply`. Note the difference in resulted data structure between `xx_apply` and `xx_mp`:

```

In [9]: xx_apply.head()
Out[9]: 0  group          SUEWS      ...
        1  group          SUEWS      ...
        2  group          SUEWS      ...
        3  group          SUEWS      ...
        4  group          SUEWS      ...
Name: (98, 2012-01-01 00:05:00), dtype: object

```

Wrap up the above code into a function for easier use in multi-grid simulations

```

In [10]: # function for multi-grid `run_supy` using map_partitions for better performance
def run_supy_mgrids(df_state_init_mgrids, df_forcing):
    dd_state_init = dd.from_pandas(
        df_state_init_mgrids,
        npartitions=os.cpu_count()*2)
    df_output_mgrids = dd_state_init\
        .map_partitions(
            lambda x: sp.run_supy(df_forcing, x)[0],
            meta=df_output)\
        .compute(scheduler='processes')
    return df_output_mgrids

```

Benchmark test

Note: this test may take a considerably long time depending on the machine performance

```
In [10]: # different running length
list_sim_len = [
    day * 288 for day in [30, 90, 120, 150, 180, 270, 365, 365 * 2, 365 * 3]
]

# number of test grids
n_grid = 12

# construct a multi-grid `df_state_init`
df_state_init_m = df_state_init.copy()
for i in range(n_grid - 1):
    df_state_init_m = df_state_init_m.append(df_state_init, ignore_index=True)

# construct a longer `df_forcing` for three years
df_forcing_m = pd.concat([df_forcing for i in range(3)])
df_forcing_m.index = pd.date_range(
    df_forcing.index[0],
    freq=df_forcing.index.freq,
    periods=df_forcing_m.index.size)

dict_time_ser = dict()
dict_time_par = dict()
for sim_len in list_sim_len:
    df_forcing_part = df_forcing_m.iloc[:sim_len]
    print('Sim days:', sim_len / 288)
    print('No. of grids:', df_state_init_m.shape[0])
    # serial run
    print('serial:')
    t0 = time()
    sp.run_supy(df_forcing_part, df_state_init_m)
    t1 = time()
    t_test = t1 - t0
    print(f'Execution time: {t_test:.2f} s')
    # print()
    dict_time_ser.update({sim_len: t_test})

    # parallel run
    print('parallel:')
    t0 = time()
    run_supy_mgrids(df_state_init_m, df_forcing_part)
    t1 = time()
    t_test = t1 - t0
    print(f'Execution time: {t_test:.2f} s')
    print()
    dict_time_par.update({sim_len: t_test})
```

```
Sim days: 30.0
No. of grids: 12
serial:
Execution time: 10.62 s
parallel:
Execution time: 3.99 s
```

```
Sim days: 90.0
No. of grids: 12
```

```
serial:  
Execution time: 37.36 s  
parallel:  
Execution time: 19.63 s
```

```
Sim days: 120.0  
No. of grids: 12  
serial:  
Execution time: 51.14 s  
parallel:  
Execution time: 28.22 s
```

```
Sim days: 150.0  
No. of grids: 12  
serial:  
Execution time: 58.08 s  
parallel:  
Execution time: 35.20 s
```

```
Sim days: 180.0  
No. of grids: 12  
serial:  
Execution time: 67.24 s  
parallel:  
Execution time: 50.90 s
```

```
Sim days: 270.0  
No. of grids: 12  
serial:  
Execution time: 97.64 s  
parallel:  
Execution time: 63.56 s
```

```
Sim days: 365.0  
No. of grids: 12  
serial:  
Execution time: 125.39 s  
parallel:  
Execution time: 66.33 s
```

```
Sim days: 730.0  
No. of grids: 12  
serial:  
Execution time: 250.16 s  
parallel:  
Execution time: 97.39 s
```

```
Sim days: 1095.0  
No. of grids: 12  
serial:  
Execution time: 381.80 s  
parallel:  
Execution time: 147.22 s
```

```
In [11]: df_benchmark = pd.DataFrame([  
        dict_time_par,  
        dict_time_ser,  
    ]).T.rename(columns={
```

```
    0: 'parallel',
    1: 'serial',
  })
df_benchmark.index = (df_benchmark.index / 288).astype(int).set_names(
    'Length of Simulation Period (day)')
# df_benchmark.columns.set_names('Execution Time (s)',inplace=True)
df_benchmark = df_benchmark\
    .assign(
        ratio=df_benchmark['parallel'] / df_benchmark['serial']
    )\
    .rename(columns={'ratio': 'ratio (=p/s, right)'})
# df_benchmark = df_benchmark.drop(index=[1,7,240])
ax = df_benchmark.plot(secondary_y='ratio (=p/s, right)',marker='o',fillstyle='none')

ax.set_ylabel('Execution Time (s)')

lines = ax.get_lines() + ax.right_ax.get_lines()
ax.legend(lines, [l.get_label() for l in lines], loc='upper center')

ax.right_ax.spines['right'].set_color('C2')
ax.right_ax.tick_params(axis='y', colors='C2')
ax.right_ax.set_ylabel('Execution Ratio (=p/s)',color='C2')
# patches,labels=ax.get_legend_handles_labels()

# ax.legend(patches,labels, loc='upper center')
```

```
Out[11]: Text(0, 0.5, 'Execution Ratio (=p/s)')
```

1.2.3 Surface properties: surface albedo

Examine the default albedo values loaded from the sample dataset

```
In [6]: df_state_init.alb
```

```
Out[6]: ind_dim  (0,)  (1,)  (2,)  (3,)  (4,)  (5,)  (6,)
        grid
        98      0.12  0.15  0.12  0.18  0.21  0.21  0.1
```

Copy the initial condition DataFrame to have a *clean slate* for our study

Note: `DataFrame.copy()` defaults to `deepcopy`

```
In [7]: df_state_init_test = df_state_init.copy()
```

Set the B1dg land cover to 100% for this study

```
In [8]: df_state_init_test.sfr = 0
        df_state_init_test.loc[:, ('sfr', '(1,)')] = 1
        df_state_init_test.sfr
```

```
Out [8]: ind_dim (0,) (1,) (2,) (3,) (4,) (5,) (6,)
         grid
         98      0      1      0      0      0      0      0
```

Construct a `df_state_init_x` dataframe to perform `supy` simulation with specified albedo

```
In [9]: # create a `df_state_init_x` with different surface properties
        n_test = 24
        list_alb_test = np.linspace(0.1, 0.8, n_test).round(2)
        df_state_init_x = df_state_init_test.append(
            [df_state_init_test]*(n_test-1), ignore_index=True)

        # here we modify surface albedo
        df_state_init_x.loc[:, ('alb', '(1,))] = list_alb_test
```

Conduct simulations with `supy`

```
In [14]: df_forcing_part = df_forcing.loc['2012 01':'2012 07']
         df_res_alb_test = run_supy_mgrids(df_state_init_x, df_forcing_part)
```

```
In [15]: df_forcing_part.iloc[[0,-1]]
```

```
Out [15]:
```

	iy	id	it	imin	qn	qh	qe	qs	qf	\
2012-01-01 00:05:00	2012	1	0	5	-999.0	-999.0	-999.0	-999.0	-999.0	
2012-07-31 23:55:00	2012	213	23	55	-999.0	-999.0	-999.0	-999.0	-999.0	
		U	...	snow	ldown	fcld	Wuh	xsmc	lai	\
2012-01-01 00:05:00	4.51500	...	-999.0	-999.0	-999.0	-999.0	-999.0	-999.0	-999.0	
2012-07-31 23:55:00	3.46125	...	-999.0	-999.0	-999.0	-999.0	-999.0	-999.0	-999.0	
		kdiff	kdir	wdir	isec					
2012-01-01 00:05:00	-999.0	-999.0	-999.0	-999.0	0.0					
2012-07-31 23:55:00	-999.0	-999.0	-999.0	-999.0	0.0					

[2 rows x 25 columns]

```
In [19]: df_res_alb_test_x=.head()
```

```
Out [19]: var
```

	Kdown					\
alb	0.10	0.13	0.16	0.19	0.22	
datetime						
2012-01-01 00:05:00	0.153333	0.153333	0.153333	0.153333	0.153333	
2012-01-01 00:10:00	0.153333	0.153333	0.153333	0.153333	0.153333	
2012-01-01 00:15:00	0.153333	0.153333	0.153333	0.153333	0.153333	
2012-01-01 00:20:00	0.153333	0.153333	0.153333	0.153333	0.153333	
2012-01-01 00:25:00	0.153333	0.153333	0.153333	0.153333	0.153333	
var						...
alb	0.25	0.28	0.31	0.34	0.37	...
datetime						...
2012-01-01 00:05:00	0.153333	0.153333	0.153333	0.153333	0.153333	...
2012-01-01 00:10:00	0.153333	0.153333	0.153333	0.153333	0.153333	...
2012-01-01 00:15:00	0.153333	0.153333	0.153333	0.153333	0.153333	...
2012-01-01 00:20:00	0.153333	0.153333	0.153333	0.153333	0.153333	...
2012-01-01 00:25:00	0.153333	0.153333	0.153333	0.153333	0.153333	...
var						...
alb	0.53	0.56	0.59	0.62	0.65	...

```

datetime
2012-01-01 00:05:00  4.504253  4.504254  4.504254  4.504255  4.504255
2012-01-01 00:10:00  4.504464  4.504465  4.504465  4.504466  4.504466
2012-01-01 00:15:00  4.504675  4.504676  4.504676  4.504677  4.504678
2012-01-01 00:20:00  4.504887  4.504887  4.504888  4.504888  4.504889
2012-01-01 00:25:00  4.505098  4.505099  4.505099  4.505100  4.505101

var
alb                0.68      0.71      0.74      0.77      0.80
datetime
2012-01-01 00:05:00  4.504256  4.504256  4.504257  4.504258  4.504258
2012-01-01 00:10:00  4.504467  4.504467  4.504468  4.504469  4.504469
2012-01-01 00:15:00  4.504678  4.504679  4.504679  4.504680  4.504680
2012-01-01 00:20:00  4.504889  4.504890  4.504891  4.504891  4.504892
2012-01-01 00:25:00  4.505101  4.505102  4.505102  4.505103  4.505103

[5 rows x 1920 columns]

```

```

In [20]: ind_alb = df_res_alb_test\
         .index\
         .set_levels(list_alb_test, level=0)\
         .set_names('alb', level=0)
df_res_alb_test.index = ind_alb
df_res_alb_test = df_res_alb_test.SUEWS.unstack(0)
df_res_alb_test_july=df_res_alb_test.loc['2012 7']

```

Examine the simulation results

```
In [21]: df_res_alb_test_july.T2.describe()
```

```

Out [21]: alb                0.10      0.13      0.16      0.19      0.22  \
count  8928.000000  8928.000000  8928.000000  8928.000000  8928.000000
mean   17.228250   17.221805   17.215353   17.208898   17.202437
std    3.329098   3.324287   3.319480   3.314680   3.309883
min    11.170041   11.169539   11.169037   11.168535   11.168033
25%    15.056289   15.055676   15.052872   15.051240   15.049831
50%    16.567200   16.563258   16.559877   16.558056   16.553386
75%    18.539557   18.528776   18.517567   18.508257   18.505134
max    29.949275   29.906529   29.863626   29.820563   29.777337

alb                0.25      0.28      0.31      0.34      0.37  ...  \
count  8928.000000  8928.000000  8928.000000  8928.000000  8928.000000  ...
mean   17.195971   17.189499   17.183020   17.176535   17.170043  ...
std    3.305090   3.300301   3.295519   3.290738   3.285962  ...
min    11.167531   11.167028   11.166526   11.166024   11.165522  ...
25%    15.047780   15.044683   15.041799   15.039364   15.037256  ...
50%    16.549466   16.548026   16.545437   16.538896   16.533971  ...
75%    18.498565   18.491591   18.483813   18.476377   18.468075  ...
max    29.733945   29.690383   29.646649   29.612174   29.587775  ...

alb                0.53      0.56      0.59      0.62      0.65  \
count  8928.000000  8928.000000  8928.000000  8928.000000  8928.000000
mean   17.135316   17.128783   17.122244   17.115696   17.109142
std    3.260573   3.255821   3.251075   3.246331   3.241592
min    11.162844   11.162341   11.161839   11.161337   11.160835
25%    15.025955   15.023428   15.021041   15.019697   15.017206
50%    16.508681   16.504471   16.497391   16.491112   16.483990
75%    18.426674   18.420512   18.411558   18.405740   18.393170
max    29.455759   29.431154   29.406500   29.381796   29.357040

```

alb	0.68	0.71	0.74	0.77	0.80
count	8928.000000	8928.000000	8928.000000	8928.000000	8928.000000
mean	17.102582	17.096015	17.089442	17.082861	17.076274
std	3.236857	3.232125	3.227395	3.222669	3.217943
min	11.160333	11.159830	11.159328	11.158826	11.158323
25%	15.015011	15.010614	15.004378	14.996300	14.993286
50%	16.480801	16.477759	16.472855	16.467660	16.462985
75%	18.384248	18.376006	18.371998	18.363307	18.354587
max	29.332234	29.307376	29.282467	29.257506	29.232492

[8 rows x 24 columns]

```
In [ ]: df_res_alb_T2_stat = df_res_alb_test_july.T2.describe()
df_res_alb_T2_diff = df_res_alb_T2_stat.transform(
    lambda x: x - df_res_alb_T2_stat.iloc[:, 0])
df_res_alb_T2_diff.columns = df_res_alb_T2_diff.columns-df_res_alb_T2_diff.columns[0]

In [32]: ax_temp_diff = df_res_alb_T2_diff.loc[['max', 'mean', 'min']].T.plot()
ax_temp_diff.set_ylabel('$\Delta T_2$ ($^{\circ}$C)')
ax_temp_diff.set_xlabel(r'$\Delta\alpha$')
ax_temp_diff.margins(x=0.2, y=0.2)
```

1.2.4 Background climate: air temperature

Examine the monthly climatology of air temperature loaded from the sample dataset

```
In [3]: df_plot = df_forcing.Tair.iloc[: -1].resample('1m').mean()
ax_temp = df_plot.plot.bar(color='tab:blue')
ax_temp.set_xticklabels(df_plot.index.strftime('%b'))
ax_temp.set_ylabel('Mean Air Temperature ($^{\circ}$C)')
ax_temp.set_xlabel('Month')
ax_temp
```

Out[3]: <matplotlib.axes._subplots.AxesSubplot at 0x12b4604e0>

Construct a function to perform parallel supy simulation with specified `diff_airtemp_test`: the difference in air temperature between the one used in simulation and loaded from sample dataset.

Note: forcing data “df_forcing” has different data structure from “df_state_init”; so we need to modify “run_supy_mgrid” to implement a “run_supy_mclims” for different climate scenarios

Let’s start the implementation of `run_supy_mclims` with a small problem of four forcing groups (i.e., climate scenarios), where the air temperatures differ from the baseline scenario with a constant bias.

```
In [4]: # save loaded sample datasets
df_forcing_part_test = df_forcing.loc['2012 1':'2012 7'].copy()
df_state_init_test = df_state_init.copy()

In [5]: # create a dict with four forcing conditions as a test
n_test = 4
list_TairDiff_test = np.linspace(0., 2, n_test).round(2)
dict_df_forcing_x = {
    tairdiff: df_forcing_part_test.copy()
```

```
    for tairdiff in list_TairDiff_test}
for tairdiff in dict_df_forcing_x:
    dict_df_forcing_x[tairdiff].loc[:, 'Tair'] += tairdiff

dd_forcing_x = {
    k: delayed(sp.run_supy)(df, df_state_init_test)[0]
    for k, df in dict_df_forcing_x.items()}

df_res_tairdiff_test0 = delayed(pd.concat)(
    dd_forcing_x,
    keys=list_TairDiff_test,
    names=['tairdiff'],
)
```

```
In [6]: # test the performance of a parallel run
t0 = time()
df_res_tairdiff_test = df_res_tairdiff_test0\
    .compute(scheduler='processes')\
    .reset_index('grid', drop=True)
t1 = time()
t_par = t1 - t0
print(f'Execution time: {t_par:.2f} s')
```

Execution time: 31.86 s

```
In [7]: # function for multi-climate `run_supy`
# wrapping the above code into one
def run_supy_mclims(df_state_init, dict_df_forcing_mclims):
    dd_forcing_x = {
        k: delayed(sp.run_supy)(df, df_state_init_test)[0]
        for k, df in dict_df_forcing_x.items()}
    df_output_mclims0 = delayed(pd.concat)(
        dd_forcing_x,
        keys=list(dict_df_forcing_x.keys()),
        names=['clm'],
    ).compute(scheduler='processes')
    df_output_mclims = df_output_mclims0.reset_index('grid', drop=True)

    return df_output_mclims
```

Construct dict_df_forcing_x with multiple forcing DataFrames

```
In [23]: # save loaded sample datasets
df_forcing_part_test = df_forcing.loc['2012 1':'2012 7'].copy()
df_state_init_test = df_state_init.copy()

# create a dict with a number of forcing conditions
n_test = 24 # can be set with a smaller value to save simulation time
list_TairDiff_test = np.linspace(0., 2, n_test).round(2)
dict_df_forcing_x = {
    tairdiff: df_forcing_part_test.copy()
    for tairdiff in list_TairDiff_test}
for tairdiff in dict_df_forcing_x:
    dict_df_forcing_x[tairdiff].loc[:, 'Tair'] += tairdiff
```

Perform simulations

```
In [24]: # run parallel simulations using `run_supy_mclims`
        t0 = time()
        df_airtemp_test_x = run_supy_mclims(df_state_init_test, dict_df_forcing_x)
        t1 = time()
        t_par = t1-t0
        print(f'Execution time: {t_par:.2f} s')
```

Execution time: 126.18 s

Examine the results

```
In [25]: df_airtemp_test = df_airtemp_test_x.SUEWS.unstack(0)
        df_temp_diff=df_airtemp_test.T2.transform(lambda x: x - df_airtemp_test.T2[0.0])
        df_temp_diff_ana=df_temp_diff.loc['2012 7']
        df_temp_diff_stat=df_temp_diff_ana.describe().loc[['max', 'mean', 'min']].T

In [26]: ax_temp_diff_stat=df_temp_diff_stat.plot()
        ax_temp_diff_stat.set_ylabel('$\Delta T_2$ ($^{\circ}$C)')
        ax_temp_diff_stat.set_xlabel('$\Delta T_a$ ($^{\circ}$C)')
        ax_temp_diff_stat.set_aspect('equal')
```

```
In [ ]:
```

End of doc/tutorial/impact-studies-parallel.ipynb

The following section was generated from docs/source/tutorial/external-interaction.ipynb

1.3 Interaction between SuPy and external models

1.3.1 Introduction

SUEWS can be coupled to other models that provide or require forcing data using the SuPy single timestep running mode. We demonstrate this feature with a simple online anthropogenic heat flux model.

Anthropogenic heat flux (Q_F) is an additional term to the surface energy balance in urban areas associated with human activities (Gabey et al., 2018; Grimmond, 1992; Nie et al., 2014; 2016; Sailor, 2011). In most cities, the largest emission source is from buildings (Hamilton et al., 2009; Iamarino et al., 2011; Sailor, 2011) and is high dependent on outdoor ambient air temperature.

load necessary packages

```
In [1]: import supy as sp
import pandas as pd
import numpy as np
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import matplotlib.dates as mdates
import seaborn as sns
%matplotlib inline
# produce high-quality figures, which can also be set as one of ['svg', 'pdf', 'retina', 'png']
# 'svg' produces high quality vector figures
from IPython.display import set_matplotlib_formats
set_matplotlib_formats('retina')
print('version info:')
print('supy:', sp.__version__)
print('supy_driver:', sp.__version_driver__)
```

```
version info:
supy: 2019.2.8
supy_driver: 2018c5
```

run SUEWS with default settings

```
In [2]: # load sample run dataset
df_state_init, df_forcing = sp.load_SampleData()
df_state_init_def=df_state_init.copy()
# set QF as zero for later comparison
df_forcing_def=df_forcing.copy()
grid=df_state_init_def.index[0]
df_state_init_def.loc[:, 'emissionsmethod']=0
df_forcing_def['qf']=0
# run supy
df_output, df_state = sp.run_supy(df_forcing_def, df_state_init_def)
df_output_def = df_output.loc[grid, 'SUEWS']
```

1.3.2 a simple QF model: `QF_simple`

model description

For demonstration purposes we have created a very simple model instead of using the SUEWS Q_F (Järvi et al. 2011) with feedback from outdoor air temperature. The simple Q_F model considers only building heating and cooling:

$$Q_F = \begin{cases} (T_2 - T_C) \times C_B, & T_2 > T_C \\ (T_H - T_2) \times H_B, & T_2 < T_H \\ Q_{F0} & \end{cases}$$

where :math: 'T_C'(:math: 'T_H') is the cooling (heating) threshold

temperature of buildings, C_B (H_B) is the building cooling (heating) rate, and Q_{F0} is the baseline anthropogenic heat. The parameters used are: C_B (H_B) set as 20 °C (10 °C), C_B (H_B) set as 1.5 W m⁻² K⁻¹ (3 W m⁻² K⁻¹) and Q_{F0} is set as 0 W m⁻², implying other building activities (e.g. lightning, water heating, computers) are zero and therefore do not change the temperature or change with temperature.

implementation

```
In [3]: def QF_simple(T2):
        qf_cooling = (T2-20)*5 if T2 > 20 else 0
        qf_heating = (10-T2)*10 if T2 < 10 else 0
        qf_res = np.max([qf_heating, qf_cooling])*0.3
        return qf_res

In [4]: ser_temp = pd.Series(
        np.arange(-5, 45, 0.5), index=np.arange(-5, 45, 0.5)).rename('temp_C')
        ser_qf_heating = ser_temp.loc[-5:10].map(QF_simple).rename(
            r'heating:$(T_h-T_a) \times H_B$')
        ser_qf_cooling = ser_temp.loc[20:45].map(QF_simple).rename(
            r'cooling: $(T_a-T_c) \times C_B$')
        ser_qf_zero = ser_temp.loc[10:20].map(QF_simple).rename('baseline: $Q_{F0}$')
        df_temp_qf = pd.concat([
            ser_temp,
            ser_qf_cooling,
            ser_qf_heating,
            ser_qf_zero,
        ],
                                axis=1).set_index('temp_C')
        ax_qf_func = df_temp_qf.plot()
        ax_qf_func.set_xlabel('$T_2$ ($^\circ$C)')
        ax_qf_func.set_ylabel('$Q_F$ (W m^{-2})')
        ax_qf_func.legend(title='simple $Q_F$')
        ax_qf_func.annotate("$T_c$",
                            xy=(20, 0), xycoords='data',
                            xytext=(25, 5), textcoords='data',
                            arrowprops=dict(arrowstyle="->", #linestyle="dashed",
                                            color="0.5",
                                            shrinkA=5, shrinkB=5,
                                            patchA=None,
                                            patchB=None,
                                            connectionstyle='arc3',
                                            ),
                            )

        ax_qf_func.annotate("$T_h$",
                            xy=(10, 0), xycoords='data',
                            xytext=(5, 5), textcoords='data',
                            arrowprops=dict(arrowstyle="->", #linestyle="dashed",
```

```

        color="0.5",
        shrinkA=5, shrinkB=5,
        patchA=None,
        patchB=None,
        connectionstyle='arc3',
    ),
)
ax_qf_func.annotate("slope: $C_B$",
                    xy=(30, QF_simple(30)), xycoords='data',
                    xytext=(20, 20), textcoords='data',
                    arrowprops=dict(arrowstyle="->", #linestyle="dashed",
                                    color="0.5",
                                    shrinkA=5, shrinkB=5,
                                    patchA=None,
                                    patchB=None,
                                    connectionstyle='arc3, rad=0.3',
                                ),
)
ax_qf_func.annotate("slope: $H_B$",
                    xy=(5, QF_simple(5)), xycoords='data',
                    xytext=(10, 20), textcoords='data',
                    arrowprops=dict(arrowstyle="->", #linestyle="dashed",
                                    color="0.5",
                                    shrinkA=5, shrinkB=5,
                                    patchA=None,
                                    patchB=None,
                                    connectionstyle='arc3, rad=-0.3',
                                ),
)
ax_qf_func.plot(10, 0, 'o', color='C1', fillstyle='none')
_ = ax_qf_func.plot(20, 0, 'o', color='C0', fillstyle='none')

```


1.3.3 communication between supy and QF_simple

construct a new coupled function

The coupling between the simple Q_F model and SuPy is done via the low-level function `suews_cal_tstep`, which is an interface function in charge of communications between SuPy frontend and the calculation kernel. By setting SuPy to receive external Q_F as forcing, at each timestep, the simple Q_F model is driven by the SuPy output T_2 and provides SuPy with Q_F , which thus forms a two-way coupled loop.

```
In [5]: # load extra low-level functions from supy to construct interactive functions
        from supy.supy_post import pack_df_output, pack_df_state
        from supy.supy_run import suews_cal_tstep, pack_grid_dict
```

```
def run_supy_qf(df_forcing_test, df_state_init_test):
    grid = df_state_init_test.index[0]
    df_state_init_test.loc[grid, 'emissionsmethod'] = 0

    df_forcing_test = df_forcing_test\
        .assign(
            metforcingdata_grid=0,
            ts5mindata_ir=0,
        )\
        .rename(
            # remanae is a workaround to resolve naming inconsistency between
            # suews fortran code interface and input forcing file headers
            columns={
                '%' + 'iy': 'iy',
                'id': 'id',
                'it': 'it',
                'imin': 'imin',
                'qn': 'qn_obs',
                'qh': 'qh_obs',
                'qe': 'qe',
                'qs': 'qs_obs',
                'qf': 'qf_obs',
                'U': 'avul',
                'RH': 'avrh',
                'Tair': 'temp_c',
                'pres': 'press_hpa',
                'rain': 'precip',
                'kdown': 'avkdn',
                'snow': 'snow_obs',
                'ldown': 'ldown_obs',
                'fcld': 'fcld_obs',
                'Wuh': 'wu_m3',
                'xsmd': 'xsmd',
                'lai': 'lai_obs',
                'kdiff': 'kdiff',
                'kdir': 'kdir',
                'wdir': 'wdir',
            }
        )

    t2_ext = df_forcing_test.iloc[0].temp_c
    qf_ext = QF_simple(t2_ext)

    # initialise dicts for holding results
```

```
dict_state = {}
dict_output = {}

# starting timestep
t_start = df_forcing_test.index[0]
# convert df to dict with `itertuples` for better performance
dict_forcing = {
    row.Index: row._asdict()
    for row in df_forcing_test.itertuples()
}
# dict_state is used to save model states for later use
dict_state = {(t_start, grid): pack_grid_dict(series_state_init)
              for grid, series_state_init in df_state_init_test.iterrows()}

# just use a single grid run for the test coupling
for timestep in df_forcing_test.index:
    # load met forcing at `timestep`
    met_forcing_timestep = dict_forcing[timestep]
    # inject `qf_ext` to `met_forcing_timestep`
    met_forcing_timestep['qf_obs'] = qf_ext

    # update model state
    dict_state_start = dict_state[(timestep, grid)]

    dict_state_end, dict_output_timestep = suews_cal_timestep(
        dict_state_start, met_forcing_timestep)
    t2_ext = dict_output_timestep['dataoutlinesuews'][-3]
    qf_ext = QF_simple(t2_ext)

    dict_output.update({(timestep, grid): dict_output_timestep})
    dict_state.update({(timestep + 1, grid): dict_state_end})

# pack results as easier DataFrames
df_output_test = pack_df_output(dict_output).swaplevel(0, 1)
df_state_test = pack_df_state(dict_state).swaplevel(0, 1)
return df_output_test.loc[grid, 'SUEWS'], df_state_test
```

simulations for summer and winter months

The simulation using SuPy coupled is performed for London 2012. The data analysed are a summer (July) and a winter (December) month. Initially Q_F is 0 W m^{-2} the T_2 is determined and used to determine $Q_{F[1]}$ which in turn modifies $T_{2[1]}$ and therefore modifies $Q_{F[2]}$ and the diagnosed $T_{2[2]}$.

spinup run (January to June) for summer simulation

```
In [6]: df_output_june, df_state_jul = sp.run_supy(
        df_forcing.loc['2012 6'], df_state_init)
        df_state_jul_init = df_state_jul.reset_index('datetime', drop=True).iloc[[-1]]
```

spinup run (July to October) for winter simulation

```
In [7]: df_output_oct, df_state_dec = sp.run_supy(
        df_forcing.loc['2012 7':'2012 11'], df_state_jul_init)
        df_state_dec_init = df_state_dec.reset_index('datetime', drop=True).iloc[[-1]]
```

coupled simulation

```
In [8]: df_output_test_summer, df_state_summer_test = run_supy_qf(
        df_forcing.loc['2012 7'], df_state_jul_init.copy())
        df_output_test_winter, df_state_winter_test = run_supy_qf(
        df_forcing.loc['2012 12'], df_state_dec_init.copy())
```

examine the results

sumer

```
In [9]: var = 'QF'
        var_label = '$Q_F$ ($ \mathrm{W \ m^{-2}}$)'
        var_label_right = '$\Delta Q_F$ ($ \mathrm{W \ m^{-2}}$)'
        period = '2012 7'
        df_test = df_output_test_summer
        y1 = df_test.loc[period, var].rename('qf_simple')
        y2 = df_output_def.loc[period, var].rename('suews')
        y3 = (y1-y2).rename('diff')
        df_plot = pd.concat([y1, y2, y3], axis=1)
        ax = df_plot.plot(secondary_y='diff')
        ax.set_ylabel(var_label)
        # sns.lmplot(data=df_plot, x='qf_simple', y='diff')
        ax.right_ax.set_ylabel(var_label_right)
        lines = ax.get_lines() + ax.right_ax.get_lines()
        ax.legend(lines, [l.get_label() for l in lines], loc='best')
```

```
Out [9]: <matplotlib.legend.Legend at 0x130455e48>
```



```
In [10]: var = 'T2'
var_label = '$T_2$ ($^{\circ}$C)'
var_label_right = '$\Delta T_2$ ($^{\circ}$C)'
period = '2012 7'
df_test = df_output_test_summer
y1 = df_test.loc[period, var].rename('qf_simple')
y2 = df_output_def.loc[period, var].rename('suews')
y3 = (y1-y2).rename('diff')
df_plot = pd.concat([y1, y2, y3], axis=1)
ax = df_plot.plot(secondary_y='diff')
ax.set_ylabel(var_label)
ax.right_ax.set_ylabel(var_label_right)
lines = ax.get_lines() + ax.right_ax.get_lines()
ax.legend(lines, [l.get_label() for l in lines], loc='best')
```

Out[10]: <matplotlib.legend.Legend at 0x1303b0208>


```
In [11]: ax_t2diff = sns.regplot(
    data=df_plot.loc[df_plot['diff'] != 0], x='qf_simple', y='diff')
ax_t2diff.set_ylabel('\Delta T$ (^{\circ}$C)')
_ = ax_t2diff.set_xlabel('Temperature (^{\circ}$C)')
```


winter

```
In [12]: var = 'QF'
var_label = '$Q_F$ ($ \mathrm{W \ m^{-2}}$)'
var_label_right = '$\Delta Q_F$ ($ \mathrm{W \ m^{-2}}$)'
period = '2012 12'
df_test = df_output_test_winter
y1 = df_test.loc[period, var].rename('qf_simple')
y2 = df_output_def.loc[period, var].rename('suews')
y3 = (y1-y2).rename('diff')
df_plot = pd.concat([y1, y2, y3], axis=1)
ax = df_plot.plot(secondary_y='diff')
ax.set_ylabel(var_label)
# sns.lmplot(data=df_plot,x='qf_simple',y='diff')
ax.right_ax.set_ylabel(var_label_right)
lines = ax.get_lines() + ax.right_ax.get_lines()
ax.legend(lines, [l.get_label() for l in lines], loc='best')
```

```
Out[12]: <matplotlib.legend.Legend at 0x10cdea828>
```



```
In [13]: var = 'T2'
var_label = '$T_2$ ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)'
var_label_right = '$\Delta T_2$ ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)'
period = '2012 12'
df_test = df_output_test_winter
y1 = df_test.loc[period, var].rename('qf_simple')
y2 = df_output_def.loc[period, var].rename('suews')
y3 = (y1-y2).rename('diff')
df_plot = pd.concat([y1, y2, y3], axis=1)
ax = df_plot.plot(secondary_y='diff')
ax.set_ylabel(var_label)
```

```
ax.right_ax.set_ylabel(var_label_right)
lines = ax.get_lines() + ax.right_ax.get_lines()
ax.legend(lines, [l.get_label() for l in lines], loc='center right')
```

Out[13]: <matplotlib.legend.Legend at 0x141a85940>


```
In [14]: %config InlineBackend.figure_format='retina'
ax_t2diff = sns.regplot(
    data=df_plot.loc[df_plot['diff'] > 0],
    x='qf_simple', y='diff')
ax_t2diff.set_ylabel('$\Delta T$ ($^{\circ}$C)')
ax_t2diff.set_xlabel('Temperature ($^{\circ}$C)')
```

Out[14]: Text(0.5, 0, 'Temperature ($^{\circ}$ C)')

comparison in $\Delta Q_F - \Delta T^2$ feedback between summer and winter

```
In [15]: # set_matplotlib_formats('retina')
df_diff_summer = (df_output_test_summer -
                  df_output_def).dropna(how='all', axis=0)
df_diff_winter = (df_output_test_winter -
                  df_output_def).dropna(how='all', axis=0)
```

```
In [16]: # set_matplotlib_formats('retina')
df_diff_season = pd.concat([
    df_diff_winter.assign(season='winter'),
    df_diff_summer.assign(season='summer'),
]).loc[:, ['season', 'QF', 'T2']]
g = sns.lmplot(
    data=df_diff_season,
    x='QF',
    y='T2',
    # col='season',
    hue='season',
    height=4,
    truncate=False,
    markers='o',
    legend_out=False,
    scatter_kws={
    # 'facecolor':'none',
        's':1,
        'zorder':0,
        'alpha':0.8,
    },
    line_kws={
    # 'facecolor':'none',
        'zorder':6,
    }
```

```

        'linestyle':'--'
    },
)
g.set_axis_labels(
    '\Delta Q_F$ ($ \mathrm{W \ m^{-2}}$)',
    '\Delta T_2$ ($^{\circ}$C)',
)
g.ax.legend(markerscale=4,title='season')
g.despine(top=False, right=False)

```

Out[16]: <seaborn.axisgrid.FacetGrid at 0x13d10d828>

The above figure indicates a positive feedback, as Q_F is increased there is an elevated T_2 but with different magnitudes. Of particular note is the positive feedback loop under warm air temperatures: the anthropogenic heat emissions increase which in turn elevates the outdoor air temperature causing yet more anthropogenic heat release. Note that London is relatively cool so the enhancement is much less than it would be in warmer cities.

End of doc/tutorial/external-interaction.ipynb

The following section was generated from docs/source/data-structure/supy-io.ipynb

Key IO Data Structures in SuPy

2.1 Introduction

The cell below demonstrates a minimal case of SuPy simulation with all key IO data structures included:

```
In [1]: import supy as sp
        df_state_init, df_forcing = sp.load_SampleData()
        df_output, df_state_final = sp.run_supy(df_forcing, df_state_init)
```

- Input: SuPy requires two DataFrames to perform a simulation, which are:

- df_state_init: model initial states;
- df_forcing: forcing data.

These input data can be loaded either through calling `load_SampleData()` as shown above or using `init_supy`. Or, based on the loaded sample DataFrames, you can modify the content to create new DataFrames for your specific needs.

- Output: The output data by SuPy consists of two DataFrames:

- df_output: model output results; this is usually the basis for scientific analysis.
- df_state_final: model final states; any of its entries can be used as a df_state_init to start another SuPy simulation.

2.2 Input

2.2.1 df_state_init: model initial states

```
In [2]: df_state_init.head()
```

```
Out[2]: var      aerodynamicresistancemethod  ah_min      ah_slope_cooling  \
        ind_dim      0      (0,)      (1,)      (0,)      (1,)
        grid
```

```

1          2.0  15.0  15.0          2.7  2.7

var      ah_slope_heating      ahprof_24hr      ...      wuprofm_24hr  \
ind_dim      (0,) (1,)      (0, 0) (0, 1) (1, 0) ...      (20, 1)
grid
1          2.7  2.7          0.57  0.65  0.45 ...      -999.0

var
ind_dim (21, 0) (21, 1) (22, 0) (22, 1) (23, 0) (23, 1)      z z0m_in zdm_in
grid
1          -999.0 -999.0 -999.0 -999.0 -999.0 -999.0 10.0  0.01  0.2

[1 rows x 1200 columns]
```

df_state_init is organised with ***grids*** in rows and ***their states*** in columns. The details of all state variables can be found in [the description page](#).

Please note the properties are stored as *flattened values* to fit into the tabular format due to the nature of DataFrame though they may actually be of higher dimension (e.g. [ahprof_24hr](#) with the dimension {24, 2}). To indicate the variable dimensionality of these properties, SuPy use the ind_dim level in columns for indices of values:

- 0 for scalars;
- (ind_dim1, ind_dim2, ...) for arrays (for a generic sense, vectors are 1D arrays).

Take ohm_coef below for example, it has a dimension of {8, 4, 3} according to [the description](#), which implies the actual values used by SuPy in simulations are passed in a layout as an array of the dimension {8, 4, 3}. As such, to get proper values passed in, users should follow the dimensionality requirement to prepare/modify df_state_init.

```

In [3]: df_state_init.loc[:, 'ohm_coef']
Out[3]: ind_dim (0, 0, 0) (0, 0, 1) (0, 0, 2) (0, 1, 0) (0, 1, 1) (0, 1, 2) \
grid
1          0.719      0.194      -36.6      0.719      0.194      -36.6

ind_dim (0, 2, 0) (0, 2, 1) (0, 2, 2) (0, 3, 0) ... (7, 0, 2) \
grid
1          0.719      0.194      -36.6      0.719      ...      -30.0

ind_dim (7, 1, 0) (7, 1, 1) (7, 1, 2) (7, 2, 0) (7, 2, 1) (7, 2, 2) \
grid
1          0.25      0.6      -30.0      0.25      0.6      -30.0

ind_dim (7, 3, 0) (7, 3, 1) (7, 3, 2)
grid
1          0.25      0.6      -30.0

[1 rows x 96 columns]
```

2.2.2 df_forcing: forcing data

df_forcing is organised with ***temporal records*** in rows and ***forcing variables*** in columns. The details of all forcing variables can be found in [the description page](#).

The missing values can be specified with -999s, which are the default NaNs accepted by SuPy and its backend SUEWS.

```

In [4]: df_forcing.head()
Out[4]:          iy  id  it  imin      qn      qh      qe      qs      qf  \
2012-01-01 00:05:00  2012  1  0      5 -999.0 -999.0 -999.0 -999.0 -999.0
```

```

2012-01-01 00:10:00 2012 1 0 10 -999.0 -999.0 -999.0 -999.0 -999.0
2012-01-01 00:15:00 2012 1 0 15 -999.0 -999.0 -999.0 -999.0 -999.0
2012-01-01 00:20:00 2012 1 0 20 -999.0 -999.0 -999.0 -999.0 -999.0
2012-01-01 00:25:00 2012 1 0 25 -999.0 -999.0 -999.0 -999.0 -999.0

      U ...      snow  ldown   fclld   Wuh   xsmd   lai   \
2012-01-01 00:05:00 4.515 ... -999.0 -999.0 -999.0 -999.0 -999.0 -999.0
2012-01-01 00:10:00 4.515 ... -999.0 -999.0 -999.0 -999.0 -999.0 -999.0
2012-01-01 00:15:00 4.515 ... -999.0 -999.0 -999.0 -999.0 -999.0 -999.0
2012-01-01 00:20:00 4.515 ... -999.0 -999.0 -999.0 -999.0 -999.0 -999.0
2012-01-01 00:25:00 4.515 ... -999.0 -999.0 -999.0 -999.0 -999.0 -999.0

      kdiff  kdir  wdir  isec
2012-01-01 00:05:00 -999.0 -999.0 -999.0 0.0
2012-01-01 00:10:00 -999.0 -999.0 -999.0 0.0
2012-01-01 00:15:00 -999.0 -999.0 -999.0 0.0
2012-01-01 00:20:00 -999.0 -999.0 -999.0 0.0
2012-01-01 00:25:00 -999.0 -999.0 -999.0 0.0

[5 rows x 25 columns]

```

Note:

The index of `df_forcing` **SHOULD BE** strictly of `DatetimeIndex` type if you want create a `df_forcing` for SuPy simulation. The SuPy runtime time-step size is instructed by the `df_forcing` with its index information.

The information below indicates SuPy will run at a 5 min (i.e. 300 s) time-step if driven by this specific `df_forcing`:

```
In [5]: freq_forcing=df_forcing.index.freq
        freq_forcing
```

```
Out [5]: <300 * Seconds>
```

2.3 Output

2.3.1 `df_output`: model output results

`df_output` is organised with ***temporal records of grids*** in rows and ***output variables of different groups*** in columns. The details of all forcing variables can be found in [the description page](#).

```
In [6]: df_output.head()
```

```

Out [6]: group
var      SUEWS
      Kdown   Kup   Ldown   Lup   Tsurf   \
grid datetime
1  2012-01-01 00:05:00 0.153333  0.0184  344.310184  372.270369  11.775916
   2012-01-01 00:10:00 0.153333  0.0184  344.310184  372.270369  11.775916
   2012-01-01 00:15:00 0.153333  0.0184  344.310184  372.270369  11.775916
   2012-01-01 00:20:00 0.153333  0.0184  344.310184  372.270369  11.775916
   2012-01-01 00:25:00 0.153333  0.0184  344.310184  372.270369  11.775916

group
var      QN   QF   QS   QH   QE   ...   \
grid datetime
1  2012-01-01 00:05:00 -27.825251  0.0 -59.305405  31.480154  0.0 ...
   2012-01-01 00:10:00 -27.825251  0.0 -59.305405  31.480154  0.0 ...
   2012-01-01 00:15:00 -27.825251  0.0 -59.305405  31.480154  0.0 ...

```

```

2012-01-01 00:20:00 -27.825251  0.0 -59.305405  31.480154  0.0 ...
2012-01-01 00:25:00 -27.825251  0.0 -59.305405  31.480154  0.0 ...

group          DailyState
var            DensSnow_Paved DensSnow_Bldgs DensSnow_EveTr
grid datetime
1  2012-01-01 00:05:00      NaN          NaN          NaN
   2012-01-01 00:10:00      NaN          NaN          NaN
   2012-01-01 00:15:00      NaN          NaN          NaN
   2012-01-01 00:20:00      NaN          NaN          NaN
   2012-01-01 00:25:00      NaN          NaN          NaN

group          DensSnow_DecTr DensSnow_Grass DensSnow_BSoil
var
grid datetime
1  2012-01-01 00:05:00      NaN          NaN          NaN
   2012-01-01 00:10:00      NaN          NaN          NaN
   2012-01-01 00:15:00      NaN          NaN          NaN
   2012-01-01 00:20:00      NaN          NaN          NaN
   2012-01-01 00:25:00      NaN          NaN          NaN

group          DensSnow_Water  a1  a2  a3
var
grid datetime
1  2012-01-01 00:05:00      NaN NaN NaN NaN
   2012-01-01 00:10:00      NaN NaN NaN NaN
   2012-01-01 00:15:00      NaN NaN NaN NaN
   2012-01-01 00:20:00      NaN NaN NaN NaN
   2012-01-01 00:25:00      NaN NaN NaN NaN

```

[5 rows x 218 columns]

df_output are recorded at the same temporal resolution as df_forcing:

```
In [7]: freq_out = df_output.index.levels[1].freq
        (freq_out, freq_out == freq_forcing)
```

Out[7]: (<300 * Seconds>, True)

2.3.2 df_state_final: model final states

df_state_final has the identical data structure as df_state_init, which facilitates the use of it as initial model states for other simulations (e.g., diagnostics of runtime model states with save_state=True set in run_supy; or simply using it as the initial conditions for future simulations starting at the ending times of previous runs).

The meanings of state variables in df_state_final can be found in [the description page](#).

```
In [8]: df_state_final.head()
```

```

Out[8]: var          aerodynamicresistancemethod ah_min
ind_dim                                0  (0,)  (1,)
grid datetime
1  2012-01-01 00:05:00          2  15.0  15.0
   2013-01-01 00:05:00          2  15.0  15.0

var          ah_slope_cooling          ah_slope_heating
ind_dim                                (0,) (1,)          (0,) (1,)
grid datetime
1  2012-01-01 00:05:00          2.7  2.7          2.7  2.7

```

```

2013-01-01 00:05:00          2.7  2.7          2.7  2.7

var          ahprof_24hr          ...  wuprofm_24hr  \
ind_dim          (0, 0) (0, 1) (1, 0)  ...          (20, 1)
grid datetime          ...
1  2012-01-01 00:05:00          0.57  0.65  0.45  ...          -999.0
   2013-01-01 00:05:00          0.57  0.65  0.45  ...          -999.0

var
ind_dim          (21, 0) (21, 1) (22, 0) (22, 1) (23, 0) (23, 1)  \
grid datetime
1  2012-01-01 00:05:00 -999.0 -999.0 -999.0 -999.0 -999.0 -999.0
   2013-01-01 00:05:00 -999.0 -999.0 -999.0 -999.0 -999.0 -999.0

var          z  z0m_in  zdm_in
ind_dim          0      0      0
grid datetime
1  2012-01-01 00:05:00  10.0  0.01  0.2
   2013-01-01 00:05:00  10.0  0.01  0.2

[2 rows x 1200 columns]

```

End of doc/data-structure/supy-io.ipynb

3.1 Top-level Functions

<code>init_supy(path_runcontrol)</code>	Initialise supy by loading initial model states.
<code>load_forcing_grid(path_runcontrol, grid)</code>	Load forcing data for a specific grid included in the index of <code>df_state_init</code> .
<code>run_supy(df_forcing, df_state_init[, save_state])</code>	Perform supy simulaiton.
<code>load_SampleData()</code>	Load sample data for quickly starting a demo run.

3.1.1 supy.init_supy

`supy.init_supy(path_runcontrol: str) → pandas.core.frame.DataFrame`
 Initialise supy by loading initial model states.

Parameters `path_runcontrol` (*str*) – Path to SUEWS RunControl.nml

Returns `df_state_init` – Initial model states. See *df_state variables* for details.

Return type `pandas.DataFrame`

Examples

```
>>> path_runcontrol = "~/SUEWS_sims/RunControl.nml" # a valid path to `RunControl.
↪nml`
>>> df_state_init = supy.init_supy(path_runcontrol)
```

3.1.2 supy.load_forcing_grid

`supy.load_forcing_grid(path_runcontrol: str, grid: int) → pandas.core.frame.DataFrame`
 Load forcing data for a specific grid included in the index of `df_state_init`.

Parameters

- **path_runcontrol** (*str*) – Path to SUEWS RunControl.nml
- **grid** (*int*) – Grid number

Returns **df_forcing** – Forcing data. See *df_forcing variables* for details.

Return type `pandas.DataFrame`

Examples

```
>>> path_runcontrol = "~/SUEWS_sims/RunControl.nml" # a valid path to_
↳ `RunControl.nml`
>>> df_state_init = supy.init_supy(path_runcontrol) # get `df_state_init`
>>> grid = df_state_init.index[0] # first grid number included in `df_state_init`
>>> df_forcing = supy.load_forcing_grid(path_runcontrol, grid) # get df_forcing
```

3.1.3 supy.run_supy

`supy.run_supy(df_forcing: pandas.core.frame.DataFrame, df_state_init: pandas.core.frame.DataFrame, save_state=False) → Tuple[pandas.core.frame.DataFrame, pandas.core.frame.DataFrame]`

Perform supy simulaiton.

Parameters

- **df_forcing** (*pandas.DataFrame*) – forcing data.
- **df_state_init** (*pandas.DataFrame*) – initial model states.
- **save_state** (*bool, optional*) – flag for saving model states at each timestep, which can be useful in diagnosing model runtime performance or performing a restart run. (the default is False, which intructs supy not to save runtime model states).

Returns

df_output, df_state_final –

- **df_output**: *output results*
- **df_state_final**: *final model states*

Return type `Tuple[pandas.DataFrame, pandas.DataFrame]`

Examples

```
>>> df_output, df_state_final = supy.run_supy(df_forcing, df_state_init)
```

3.1.4 supy.load_SampleData

`supy.load_SampleData() → Tuple[pandas.core.frame.DataFrame, pandas.core.frame.DataFrame]`
Load sample data for quickly starting a demo run.

Returns

df_state_init, df_forcing –

- `df_state_init`: *initial model states*
- `df_forcing`: *forcing data*

Return type Tuple[pandas.DataFrame, pandas.DataFrame]

Examples

```
>>> df_state_init, df_forcing = supy.load_SampleData()
```

3.2 Key Data Structures

3.2.1 `df_state` variables

`aerodynamicresistancemethod`

Description Internal use. Please DO NOT modify

Dimensionality 0

Dimensionality Remarks Scalar

SUEWS-related variables None

`ah_min`

Description Minimum QF values.

Dimensionality (2,)

Dimensionality Remarks 2: {Weekday, Weekend}

SUEWS-related variables `AHMin_WD`, `AHMin_WE`

`ah_slope_cooling`

Description Cooling slope of QF calculation.

Dimensionality (2,)

Dimensionality Remarks 2: {Weekday, Weekend}

SUEWS-related variables `AHSlope_Cooling_WD`, `AHSlope_Cooling_WE`

`ah_slope_heating`

Description Heating slope of QF calculation.

Dimensionality (2,)

Dimensionality Remarks 2: {Weekday, Weekend}

SUEWS-related variables `AHSlope_Heating_WD`, `AHSlope_Heating_WE`

`ahprof_24hr`

Description Hourly profile values used in energy use calculation.

Dimensionality (24, 2)

Dimensionality Remarks 24: hours of a day

2: {Weekday, Weekend}

SUEWS-related variables `EnergyUseProfWD, EnergyUseProfWE`

alb

Description Effective surface albedo (middle of the day value) for summertime.

Dimensionality (7,)

Dimensionality Remarks 7: { Paved, Bldgs, EveTr, DecTr, Grass, BSoil, Water}

SUEWS-related variables `AlbedoMax`

albdectr_id

Description Albedo of deciduous surface `DecTr` on day 0 of run

Dimensionality 0

Dimensionality Remarks Scalar

SUEWS-related variables `albDecTr0`

albevetr_id

Description Albedo of evergreen surface `EveTr` on day 0 of run

Dimensionality 0

Dimensionality Remarks Scalar

SUEWS-related variables `albEveTr0`

albgrass_id

Description Albedo of grass surface `Grass` on day 0 of run

Dimensionality 0

Dimensionality Remarks Scalar

SUEWS-related variables `albGrass0`

albmax_dectr

Description Effective surface albedo (middle of the day value) for summertime.

Dimensionality 0

Dimensionality Remarks Scalar

SUEWS-related variables `AlbedoMax`

albmax_evertr

Description Effective surface albedo (middle of the day value) for summertime.

Dimensionality 0

Dimensionality Remarks Scalar

SUEWS-related variables `AlbedoMax`

albmax_grass

Description Effective surface albedo (middle of the day value) for summertime.

Dimensionality 0

Dimensionality Remarks Scalar

SUEWS-related variables `AlbedoMax`

albmin_dectr

Description Effective surface albedo (middle of the day value) for wintertime (not including snow).

Dimensionality 0

Dimensionality Remarks Scalar

SUEWS-related variables `AlbedoMin`

albmin_evetr

Description Effective surface albedo (middle of the day value) for wintertime (not including snow).

Dimensionality 0

Dimensionality Remarks Scalar

SUEWS-related variables `AlbedoMin`

albmin_grass

Description Effective surface albedo (middle of the day value) for wintertime (not including snow).

Dimensionality 0

Dimensionality Remarks Scalar

SUEWS-related variables `AlbedoMin`

alpha_bioco2

Description The mean apparent ecosystem quantum. Represents the initial slope of the light-response curve.

Dimensionality (3,)

Dimensionality Remarks 3: { `EveTr`, `DecTr`, `Grass` }

SUEWS-related variables `alpha`

alpha_enh_bioco2

Description Part of the `alpha` coefficient related to the fraction of vegetation.

Dimensionality (3,)

Dimensionality Remarks 3: { `EveTr`, `DecTr`, `Grass` }

SUEWS-related variables `alpha_enh`

alt

Description Used for both the radiation and water flow between grids.

Dimensionality 0

Dimensionality Remarks Scalar

SUEWS-related variables `Alt`

baset

Description Base Temperature for initiating growing degree days (GDD) for leaf growth. [°C]

Dimensionality (3,)

Dimensionality Remarks 3: { `EveTr`, `DecTr`, `Grass` }

SUEWS-related variables `BaseT`

basete

Description Base temperature for initiating senescence degree days (SDD) for leaf off. [°C]

Dimensionality (3,)

Dimensionality Remarks 3: { EveTr, DecTr, Grass }

SUEWS-related variables BaseTe

basethdd

Description Base temperature for heating degree days [°C]

Dimensionality 0

Dimensionality Remarks Scalar

SUEWS-related variables BaseTHDD

beta_bioco2

Description The light-saturated gross photosynthesis of the canopy. [$\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$]

Dimensionality (3,)

Dimensionality Remarks 3: { EveTr, DecTr, Grass }

SUEWS-related variables beta

beta_enh_bioco2

Description Part of the `beta` coefficient related to the fraction of vegetation.

Dimensionality (3,)

Dimensionality Remarks 3: { EveTr, DecTr, Grass }

SUEWS-related variables beta_enh

bldgh

Description Mean building height [m]

Dimensionality 0

Dimensionality Remarks Scalar

SUEWS-related variables H_Bldgs

capmax_dec

Description Maximum water storage capacity for upper surfaces (i.e. canopy)

Dimensionality 0

Dimensionality Remarks Scalar

SUEWS-related variables StorageMax

capmin_dec

Description Minimum water storage capacity for upper surfaces (i.e. canopy).

Dimensionality 0

Dimensionality Remarks Scalar

SUEWS-related variables StorageMin

chanohm

Description Bulk transfer coefficient for this surface to use in AnOHM [-]

Dimensionality (7,)

Dimensionality Remarks 7: { Paved, Bldgs, EveTr, DecTr, Grass, BSoil, Water }

SUEWS-related variables AnOHM_Ch

cpanohm

Description Volumetric heat capacity for this surface to use in AnOHM [J m^{-3}]

Dimensionality (7,)

Dimensionality Remarks 7: { Paved, Bldgs, EveTr, DecTr, Grass, BSoil, Water }

SUEWS-related variables AnOHM_Cp

crwmax

Description Maximum water holding capacity of snow [mm]

Dimensionality 0

Dimensionality Remarks Scalar

SUEWS-related variables CRWMax

crwmin

Description Minimum water holding capacity of snow [mm]

Dimensionality 0

Dimensionality Remarks Scalar

SUEWS-related variables CRWMin

daywat

Description Irrigation flag: 1 for on and 0 for off.

Dimensionality (7,)

Dimensionality Remarks 7: { Sunday, Monday, Tuesday, Wednesday, Thursday, Friday, Saturday }

SUEWS-related variables DayWat (1), DayWat (2), DayWat (3), DayWat (4), DayWat (5), DayWat (6), DayWat (7)

daywatper

Description Fraction of properties using irrigation for each day of a week.

Dimensionality (7,)

Dimensionality Remarks 7: { Sunday, Monday, Tuesday, Wednesday, Thursday, Friday, Saturday }

SUEWS-related variables DayWatPer (1), DayWatPer (2), DayWatPer (3), DayWatPer (4), DayWatPer (5), DayWatPer (6), DayWatPer (7)

decidcap_id

Description Storage capacity of deciduous surface DecTr on day 0 of run.

Dimensionality 0

Dimensionality Remarks Scalar

SUEWS-related variables decidCap0

dectreeh

Description Mean height of deciduous trees [m]

Dimensionality 0

Dimensionality Remarks Scalar

SUEWS-related variables `H_DecTr`

diagnose

Description Internal use. Please DO NOT modify

Dimensionality 0

Dimensionality Remarks Scalar

SUEWS-related variables None

diagqn

Description Internal use. Please DO NOT modify

Dimensionality 0

Dimensionality Remarks Scalar

SUEWS-related variables None

diagqs

Description Internal use. Please DO NOT modify

Dimensionality 0

Dimensionality Remarks Scalar

SUEWS-related variables None

drainrt

Description Drainage rate of bucket for LUMPS [mm h⁻¹]

Dimensionality 0

Dimensionality Remarks Scalar

SUEWS-related variables `LUMPS_DrRate`

ef_umolco2perj

Description Emission factor for fuels used for building heating.

Dimensionality 0

Dimensionality Remarks Scalar

SUEWS-related variables `EF_umolCO2perJ`

emis

Description Effective surface emissivity.

Dimensionality (7,)

Dimensionality Remarks 7: { Paved, Bldgs, EveTr, DecTr, Grass, BSoil, Water }

SUEWS-related variables `Emissivity`

emissionsmethod

Description Determines method for QF calculation.

Dimensionality 0
Dimensionality Remarks Scalar
SUEWS-related variables `EmissionsMethod`

enddls

Description End of the day light savings [DOY]
Dimensionality 0
Dimensionality Remarks Scalar
SUEWS-related variables `EndDLS`

enef_v_jkm

Description Emission factor for heat [J km^{-1}].
Dimensionality 0
Dimensionality Remarks Scalar
SUEWS-related variables `EnEF_v_Jkm`

evapmethod

Description Internal use. Please DO NOT modify
Dimensionality 0
Dimensionality Remarks Scalar
SUEWS-related variables None

evetreeh

Description Mean height of evergreen trees [m]
Dimensionality 0
Dimensionality Remarks Scalar
SUEWS-related variables `H_EveTr`

faibldg

Description Frontal area index for buildings [-]
Dimensionality 0
Dimensionality Remarks Scalar
SUEWS-related variables `FAI_Bldgs`

faidectree

Description Frontal area index for deciduous trees [-]
Dimensionality 0
Dimensionality Remarks Scalar
SUEWS-related variables `FAI_DecTr`

faievetree

Description Frontal area index for evergreen trees [-]
Dimensionality 0

Dimensionality Remarks Scalar

SUEWS-related variables `FAI_EveTr`

faut

Description Fraction of irrigated area that is irrigated using automated systems

Dimensionality 0

Dimensionality Remarks Scalar

SUEWS-related variables `Faut`

fcef_v_kgkm

Description CO2 emission factor [kg km^{-1}]

Dimensionality 0

Dimensionality Remarks Scalar

SUEWS-related variables `FcEF_v_kgkm`

flowchange

Description Difference in input and output flows for water surface [mm h^{-1}]

Dimensionality 0

Dimensionality Remarks Scalar

SUEWS-related variables `FlowChange`

frfossilfuel_heat

Description Fraction of fossil fuels used for building heating [-]

Dimensionality 0

Dimensionality Remarks Scalar

SUEWS-related variables `FrFossilFuel_Heat`

frfossilfuel_nonheat

Description Fraction of fossil fuels used for building energy use [-]

Dimensionality 0

Dimensionality Remarks Scalar

SUEWS-related variables `FrFossilFuel_NonHeat`

g1

Description Related to maximum surface conductance [mm s^{-1}]

Dimensionality 0

Dimensionality Remarks Scalar

SUEWS-related variables `G1`

g2

Description Related to Kdown dependence [W m^{-2}]

Dimensionality 0

Dimensionality Remarks Scalar

SUEWS-related variables [G2](#)

g3

Description Related to VPD dependence [units depend on [gsModel](#)]

Dimensionality 0

Dimensionality Remarks Scalar

SUEWS-related variables [G3](#)

g4

Description Related to VPD dependence [units depend on [gsModel](#)]

Dimensionality 0

Dimensionality Remarks Scalar

SUEWS-related variables [G4](#)

g5

Description Related to temperature dependence [°C]

Dimensionality 0

Dimensionality Remarks Scalar

SUEWS-related variables [G5](#)

g6

Description Related to soil moisture dependence [mm^{-1}]

Dimensionality 0

Dimensionality Remarks Scalar

SUEWS-related variables [G6](#)

gddf11

Description The growing degree days (GDD) needed for full capacity of the leaf area index (LAI) [°C].

Dimensionality (3,)

Dimensionality Remarks 3: { [EveTr](#), [DecTr](#), [Grass](#) }

SUEWS-related variables [GDDFull](#)

gsmodel

Description Formulation choice for conductance calculation.

Dimensionality 0

Dimensionality Remarks Scalar

SUEWS-related variables [gsModel](#)

humactivity_24hr

Description Hourly profile values used in human activity calculation.

Dimensionality (24, 2)

Dimensionality Remarks 24: hours of a day

2: {Weekday, Weekend}

SUEWS-related variables `ActivityProfWD, ActivityProfWE`

`ie_a`

Description Coefficient for automatic irrigation model.

Dimensionality (3,)

Dimensionality Remarks 3: { `EveTr`, `DecTr`, `Grass`}

SUEWS-related variables `Ie_a1, Ie_a2, Ie_a3`

`ie_end`

Description Day when irrigation ends [DOY]

Dimensionality 0

Dimensionality Remarks Scalar

SUEWS-related variables `Ie_end`

`ie_m`

Description Coefficient for manual irrigation model.

Dimensionality (3,)

Dimensionality Remarks 3: { `EveTr`, `DecTr`, `Grass`}

SUEWS-related variables `Ie_m1, Ie_m2, Ie_m3`

`ie_start`

Description Day when irrigation starts [DOY]

Dimensionality 0

Dimensionality Remarks Scalar

SUEWS-related variables `Ie_start`

`internalwateruse_h`

Description Internal water use [mm h⁻¹]

Dimensionality 0

Dimensionality Remarks Scalar

SUEWS-related variables `InternalWaterUse`

`irrfraconif`

Description Fraction of evergreen trees that are irrigated [-]

Dimensionality 0

Dimensionality Remarks Scalar

SUEWS-related variables `IrrFr_EveTr`

`irrfra decid`

Description Fraction of deciduous trees that are irrigated [-]

Dimensionality 0

Dimensionality Remarks Scalar

SUEWS-related variables `IrrFr_DecTr`

irrffracgrass

Description Fraction of Grass that is irrigated [-]

Dimensionality 0

Dimensionality Remarks Scalar

SUEWS-related variables `IrrFr_Grass`

kkanohm

Description Thermal conductivity for this surface to use in AnOHM [W m K^{-1}]

Dimensionality (7,)

Dimensionality Remarks 7: { Paved, Bldgs, EveTr, DecTr, Grass, BSoil, Water}

SUEWS-related variables `AnOHM_Kk`

kmax

Description Maximum incoming shortwave radiation [W m^{-2}]

Dimensionality 0

Dimensionality Remarks Scalar

SUEWS-related variables `Kmax`

lai_id

Description Initial LAI values.

Dimensionality (3,)

Dimensionality Remarks 3: { EveTr, DecTr, Grass}

SUEWS-related variables `LAIinitialDecTr`, `LAIinitialEveTr`, `LAIinitialGrass`

laicalcyes

Description Internal use. Please DO NOT modify

Dimensionality 0

Dimensionality Remarks Scalar

SUEWS-related variables None

laimax

Description full leaf-on summertime value

Dimensionality (3,)

Dimensionality Remarks 3: { EveTr, DecTr, Grass}

SUEWS-related variables `LAIMax`

laimin

Description leaf-off wintertime value

Dimensionality (3,)

Dimensionality Remarks 3: { EveTr, DecTr, Grass}

SUEWS-related variables `LAIMin`

`laipower`

Description parameters required by LAI calculation.

Dimensionality (4, 3)

Dimensionality Remarks 4: {LeafGrowthPower1, LeafGrowthPower2, LeafOffPower1, LeafOffPower2}

3: { EveTr, DecTr, Grass }

SUEWS-related variables `LeafGrowthPower1`, `LeafGrowthPower2`, `LeafOffPower1`, `LeafOffPower2`

`laitype`

Description LAI calculation choice.

Dimensionality (3,)

Dimensionality Remarks 3: { EveTr, DecTr, Grass }

SUEWS-related variables `LAIEq`

`lat`

Description Latitude [deg].

Dimensionality 0

Dimensionality Remarks Scalar

SUEWS-related variables `lat`

`lng`

Description longitude [deg]

Dimensionality 0

Dimensionality Remarks Scalar

SUEWS-related variables `lng`

`maxconductance`

Description The maximum conductance of each vegetation or surface type. [mm s^{-1}]

Dimensionality (3,)

Dimensionality Remarks 3: { EveTr, DecTr, Grass }

SUEWS-related variables `MaxConductance`

`maxqfmetab`

Description Maximum value for human heat emission. [W m^{-2}]

Dimensionality 0

Dimensionality Remarks Scalar

SUEWS-related variables `MaxQFMetab`

`min_res_bioco2`

Description Minimum soil respiration rate (for cold-temperature limit) [$\text{umol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$].

Dimensionality (3,)

Dimensionality Remarks 3: { EveTr, DecTr, Grass}

SUEWS-related variables `min_respi`

minqfmetab

Description Minimum value for human heat emission. [W m^{-2}]

Dimensionality 0

Dimensionality Remarks Scalar

SUEWS-related variables `MinQFMetab`

narp_emis_snow

Description Effective surface emissivity.

Dimensionality 0

Dimensionality Remarks Scalar

SUEWS-related variables `Emissivity`

narp_trans_site

Description Atmospheric transmissivity for NARP [-]

Dimensionality 0

Dimensionality Remarks Scalar

SUEWS-related variables `NARP_Trans`

netradiationmethod

Description Determines method for calculation of radiation fluxes.

Dimensionality 0

Dimensionality Remarks Scalar

SUEWS-related variables `NetRadiationMethod`

ohm_coef

Description Coefficients for OHM calculation.

Dimensionality (8, 4, 3)

Dimensionality Remarks 8: { Paved, Bldgs, EveTr, DecTr, Grass, BSoil, Water, one extra land cover type (currently NOT used)}

4: {SummerWet, SummerDry, WinterWet, WinterDry}

3: {a1, a2, a3}

SUEWS-related variables `a1, a2, a3`

ohm_threshsw

Description Temperature threshold determining whether summer/winter OHM coefficients are applied [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]

Dimensionality (8,)

Dimensionality Remarks 8: { Paved, Bldgs, EveTr, DecTr, Grass, BSoil, Water, one extra land cover type (currently NOT used)}

SUEWS-related variables `OHMThresh_SW`

`ohm_threshwd`

Description Soil moisture threshold determining whether wet/dry OHM coefficients are applied [-]

Dimensionality (8,)

Dimensionality Remarks 8: { Paved, Bldgs, EveTr, DecTr, Grass, BSoil, Water, one extra land cover type (currently NOT used)}

SUEWS-related variables `OHMThresh_WD`

`ohmincqw`

Description Determines whether the storage heat flux calculation uses Q^* or ($Q^* + QF$).

Dimensionality 0

Dimensionality Remarks Scalar

SUEWS-related variables `OHMIncQF`

`pipecapacity`

Description Storage capacity of pipes [mm]

Dimensionality 0

Dimensionality Remarks Scalar

SUEWS-related variables `PipeCapacity`

`popdensdaytime`

Description Daytime population density (i.e. workers, tourists) [people ha⁻¹]

Dimensionality 0

Dimensionality Remarks Scalar

SUEWS-related variables `PopDensDay`

`popdensnighttime`

Description Night-time population density (i.e. residents) [people ha⁻¹]

Dimensionality 0

Dimensionality Remarks Scalar

SUEWS-related variables `PopDensNight`

`popprof_24hr`

Description Hourly profile values used in dynamic population estimation.

Dimensionality (24, 2)

Dimensionality Remarks 24: hours of a day

2: {Weekday, Weekend}

SUEWS-related variables `PopProfWD, PopProfWE`

`pormax_dec`

Description full leaf-on summertime value Used only for DecTr (can affect roughness calculation)

Dimensionality 0

Dimensionality Remarks Scalar

SUEWS-related variables `PorosityMax`

`pormin_dec`

Description leaf-off wintertime value Used only for `DecTr` (can affect roughness calculation)

Dimensionality 0

Dimensionality Remarks Scalar

SUEWS-related variables `PorosityMin`

`porosity_id`

Description Porosity of deciduous vegetation on day 0 of run.

Dimensionality 0

Dimensionality Remarks Scalar

SUEWS-related variables `porosity0`

`preciplimit`

Description Limit for hourly snowfall when the ground is fully covered with snow [mm]

Dimensionality 0

Dimensionality Remarks Scalar

SUEWS-related variables `PrecipLimSnow`

`preciplimitalb`

Description Limit for hourly precipitation when the ground is fully covered with snow. Then snow albedo is reset to `AlbedoMax` [mm]

Dimensionality 0

Dimensionality Remarks Scalar

SUEWS-related variables `PrecipLimAlb`

`qf0_beu`

Description Building energy use [W m^{-2}]

Dimensionality (2,)

Dimensionality Remarks 2: {Weekday, Weekend}

SUEWS-related variables `QF0_BEU_WD`, `QF0_BEU_WE`

`qf_a`

Description Base value for QF calculation.

Dimensionality (2,)

Dimensionality Remarks 2: {Weekday, Weekend}

SUEWS-related variables `QF_A_WD`, `QF_A_WE`

`qf_b`

Description Parameter related to heating degree days.

Dimensionality (2,)

Dimensionality Remarks 2: {Weekday, Weekend}

SUEWS-related variables `QF_B_WD`, `QF_B_WE`

`qf_c`

Description Parameter related to heating degree days.

Dimensionality (2,)

Dimensionality Remarks 2: {Weekday, Weekend}

SUEWS-related variables `QF_C_WD`, `QF_C_WE`

`radmeltfact`

Description Hourly radiation melt factor of snow [$\text{mm W}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$]

Dimensionality 0

Dimensionality Remarks Scalar

SUEWS-related variables `RadMeltFactor`

`raincover`

Description Limit when surface totally covered with water for LUMPS [mm]

Dimensionality 0

Dimensionality Remarks Scalar

SUEWS-related variables `LUMPS_Cover`

`rainmaxres`

Description Maximum water bucket reservoir [mm] Used for LUMPS surface wetness control.

Dimensionality 0

Dimensionality Remarks Scalar

SUEWS-related variables `LUMPS_MaxRes`

`resp_a`

Description Respiration coefficient a.

Dimensionality (3,)

Dimensionality Remarks 3: { `EveTr`, `DecTr`, `Grass` }

SUEWS-related variables `resp_a`

`resp_b`

Description Respiration coefficient b - related to air temperature dependency.

Dimensionality (3,)

Dimensionality Remarks 3: { `EveTr`, `DecTr`, `Grass` }

SUEWS-related variables `resp_b`

`roughlenheatmethod`

Description Determines method for calculating roughness length for heat.

Dimensionality 0

Dimensionality Remarks Scalar

SUEWS-related variables `RoughLenHeatMethod`

roughlenmommethode

Description Determines how aerodynamic roughness length (z_{0m}) and zero displacement height (z_{dm}) are calculated.

Dimensionality 0

Dimensionality Remarks Scalar

SUEWS-related variables `RoughLenMomMethod`

runofftowater

Description Fraction of above-ground runoff flowing to water surface during flooding [-]

Dimensionality 0

Dimensionality Remarks Scalar

SUEWS-related variables `RunoffToWater`

s1

Description A parameter related to soil moisture dependence [-]

Dimensionality 0

Dimensionality Remarks Scalar

SUEWS-related variables `S1`

s2

Description A parameter related to soil moisture dependence [mm]

Dimensionality 0

Dimensionality Remarks Scalar

SUEWS-related variables `S2`

sathydraulicconduct

Description Hydraulic conductivity for saturated soil [mm s^{-1}]

Dimensionality (7,)

Dimensionality Remarks 7: { `Paved`, `Bldgs`, `EveTr`, `DecTr`, `Grass`, `BSoil`, `Water` }

SUEWS-related variables `SatHydraulicCond`

sddfll

Description The senseence degree days (SDD) needed to initiate leaf off. [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]

Dimensionality (3,)

Dimensionality Remarks 3: { `EveTr`, `DecTr`, `Grass` }

SUEWS-related variables `SDDFull`

sfr

Description Surface cover fractions.

Dimensionality (7,)

Dimensionality Remarks 7: { `Paved`, `Bldgs`, `EveTr`, `DecTr`, `Grass`, `BSoil`, `Water` }

SUEWS-related variables `Fr_Bldgs`, `Fr_Bsoil`, `Fr_DecTr`, `Fr_EveTr`, `Fr_Grass`, `Fr_Paved`, `Fr_Water`

smdmethod

Description Determines method for calculating soil moisture deficit (SMD).

Dimensionality 0

Dimensionality Remarks Scalar

SUEWS-related variables `SMDMethod`

snowalb

Description Initial snow albedo

Dimensionality 0

Dimensionality Remarks Scalar

SUEWS-related variables `SnowAlb0`

snowalbmax

Description Effective surface albedo (middle of the day value) for summertime.

Dimensionality 0

Dimensionality Remarks Scalar

SUEWS-related variables `AlbedoMax`

snowalbmin

Description Effective surface albedo (middle of the day value) for wintertime (not including snow).

Dimensionality 0

Dimensionality Remarks Scalar

SUEWS-related variables `AlbedoMin`

snowdens

Description Initial snow density of each land cover.

Dimensionality (7,)

Dimensionality Remarks 7: { Paved, Bldgs, EveTr, DecTr, Grass, BSoil, Water }

SUEWS-related variables `SnowDensBldgs`, `SnowDensPaved`, `SnowDensDecTr`,
`SnowDensEveTr`, `SnowDensGrass`, `SnowDensBSoil`, `SnowDensWater`

snowdensmax

Description Maximum snow density [kg m^{-3}]

Dimensionality 0

Dimensionality Remarks Scalar

SUEWS-related variables `SnowDensMax`

snowdensmin

Description Fresh snow density [kg m^{-3}]

Dimensionality 0

Dimensionality Remarks Scalar

SUEWS-related variables `SnowDensMin`

snowfrac

Description Initial plan area fraction of snow on each land cover

Dimensionality (7,)

Dimensionality Remarks 7: { Paved, Bldgs, EveTr, DecTr, Grass, BSoil, Water }

SUEWS-related variables `SnowFracBldgs`, `SnowFracPaved`, `SnowFracDecTr`,
`SnowFracEveTr`, `SnowFracGrass`, `SnowFracBSoil`, `SnowFracWater`

snowlimbldg

Description Limit of the snow water equivalent for snow removal from roads and roofs [mm]

Dimensionality 0

Dimensionality Remarks Scalar

SUEWS-related variables `SnowLimRemove`

snowlimpaved

Description Limit of the snow water equivalent for snow removal from roads and roofs [mm]

Dimensionality 0

Dimensionality Remarks Scalar

SUEWS-related variables `SnowLimRemove`

snowpack

Description Initial snow water equivalent on each land cover

Dimensionality (7,)

Dimensionality Remarks 7: { Paved, Bldgs, EveTr, DecTr, Grass, BSoil, Water }

SUEWS-related variables `SnowPackBldgs`, `SnowPackPaved`, `SnowPackDecTr`,
`SnowPackEveTr`, `SnowPackGrass`, `SnowPackBSoil`, `SnowPackWater`

snowpacklimit

Description Limit for the snow water equivalent when snow cover starts to be patchy [mm]

Dimensionality (7,)

Dimensionality Remarks 7: { Paved, Bldgs, EveTr, DecTr, Grass, BSoil, Water }

SUEWS-related variables `SnowLimPatch`

snowprof_24hr

Description Hourly profile values used in snow clearing.

Dimensionality (24, 2)

Dimensionality Remarks 24: hours of a day

2: { Weekday, Weekend }

SUEWS-related variables `SnowClearingProfWD`, `SnowClearingProfWE`

snowuse

Description Determines whether the snow part of the model runs.

Dimensionality 0

Dimensionality Remarks Scalar

SUEWS-related variables `SnowUse`

snowwater

Description Initial amount of liquid water in the snow on each land cover

Dimensionality (7,)

Dimensionality Remarks 7: { Paved, Bldgs, EveTr, DecTr, Grass, BSoil, Water}

SUEWS-related variables `SnowWaterBldgsState`, `SnowWaterPavedState`,
`SnowWaterDecTrState`, `SnowWaterEveTrState`, `SnowWaterGrassState`,
`SnowWaterBSoilState`, `SnowWaterWaterState`

soildepth

Description Depth of soil beneath the surface [mm]

Dimensionality (7,)

Dimensionality Remarks 7: { Paved, Bldgs, EveTr, DecTr, Grass, BSoil, Water}

SUEWS-related variables `SoilDepth`

soilstore_id

Description Initial water stored in soil beneath each land cover

Dimensionality (7,)

Dimensionality Remarks 7: { Paved, Bldgs, EveTr, DecTr, Grass, BSoil, Water}

SUEWS-related variables `SoilstoreBldgsState`, `SoilstorePavedState`,
`SoilstoreDecTrState`, `SoilstoreEveTrState`, `SoilstoreGrassState`,
`SoilstoreBSoilState`

soilstorecap

Description Limit value for `SoilDepth` [mm]

Dimensionality (7,)

Dimensionality Remarks 7: { Paved, Bldgs, EveTr, DecTr, Grass, BSoil, Water}

SUEWS-related variables `SoilStoreCap`

stabilitymethod

Description Defines which atmospheric stability functions are used.

Dimensionality 0

Dimensionality Remarks Scalar

SUEWS-related variables `StabilityMethod`

startdls

Description Start of the day light savings [DOY]

Dimensionality 0

Dimensionality Remarks Scalar

SUEWS-related variables `StartDLS`

state_id

Description Initial wetness condition on each land cover

Dimensionality (7,)

Dimensionality Remarks 7: { Paved, Bldgs, EveTr, DecTr, Grass, BSoil, Water}

SUEWS-related variables BldgsState, PavedState, DecTrState, EveTrState, GrassState, BSoilState, WaterState

statelimit

Description Upper limit to the surface state. [mm]

Dimensionality (7,)

Dimensionality Remarks 7: { Paved, Bldgs, EveTr, DecTr, Grass, BSoil, Water}

SUEWS-related variables StateLimit

storageheatmethod

Description Determines method for calculating storage heat flux ΔQ_S .

Dimensionality 0

Dimensionality Remarks Scalar

SUEWS-related variables StorageHeatMethod

storedrainprm

Description Coefficients used in drainage calculation.

Dimensionality (6, 7)

Dimensionality Remarks 6: { StorageMin, DrainageEq, DrainageCoef1, DrainageCoef2, StorageMax, current storage}

7: { Paved, Bldgs, EveTr, DecTr, Grass, BSoil, Water}

SUEWS-related variables DrainageCoef1, DrainageCoef2, DrainageEq, StorageMax, StorageMin

surfacearea

Description Area of the grid [ha].

Dimensionality 0

Dimensionality Remarks Scalar

SUEWS-related variables SurfaceArea

t_critic_cooling

Description Critical cooling temperature.

Dimensionality (2,)

Dimensionality Remarks 2: {Weekday, Weekend}

SUEWS-related variables TCritic_Cooling_WD, TCritic_Cooling_WE

t_critic_heating

Description Critical heating temperature.

Dimensionality (2,)

Dimensionality Remarks 2: {Weekday, Weekend}

SUEWS-related variables TCritic_Heating_WD, TCritic_Heating_WE

tau_a

Description Time constant for snow albedo aging in cold snow [-]

Dimensionality 0

Dimensionality Remarks Scalar

SUEWS-related variables `tau_a`

tau_f

Description Time constant for snow albedo aging in melting snow [-]

Dimensionality 0

Dimensionality Remarks Scalar

SUEWS-related variables `tau_f`

tau_r

Description Time constant for snow density ageing [-]

Dimensionality 0

Dimensionality Remarks Scalar

SUEWS-related variables `tau_r`

tempmeltfact

Description Hourly temperature melt factor of snow [mm K⁻¹ h⁻¹]

Dimensionality 0

Dimensionality Remarks Scalar

SUEWS-related variables `TempMeltFactor`

th

Description Upper air temperature limit [°C]

Dimensionality 0

Dimensionality Remarks Scalar

SUEWS-related variables `TH`

theta_bioco2

Description The convexity of the curve at light saturation.

Dimensionality (3,)

Dimensionality Remarks 3: { `EveTr`, `DecTr`, `Grass` }

SUEWS-related variables `theta`

timezone

Description Time zone [h] for site relative to UTC (east is positive). This should be set according to the times given in the meteorological forcing file(s).

Dimensionality 0

Dimensionality Remarks Scalar

SUEWS-related variables `Timezone`

t1**Description** Lower air temperature limit [°C]**Dimensionality** 0**Dimensionality Remarks** Scalar**SUEWS-related variables** TL**trafficrate****Description** Traffic rate used for CO2 flux calculation.**Dimensionality** (2,)**Dimensionality Remarks** 2: {Weekday, Weekend}**SUEWS-related variables** TrafficRate_WD, TrafficRate_WE**trafficunits****Description** Units for the traffic rate for the study area. Not used in v2018a.**Dimensionality** 0**Dimensionality Remarks** Scalar**SUEWS-related variables** TrafficUnits**traffprof_24hr****Description** Hourly profile values used in traffic activity calculation.**Dimensionality** (24, 2)**Dimensionality Remarks** 24: hours of a day

2: {Weekday, Weekend}

SUEWS-related variables TraffProfWD, TraffProfWE**tstep****Description** Specifies the model time step [s].**Dimensionality** 0**Dimensionality Remarks** Scalar**SUEWS-related variables** Tstep**veg_type****Description** Internal use. Please DO NOT modify**Dimensionality** 0**Dimensionality Remarks** Scalar**SUEWS-related variables** None**waterdist****Description** Fraction of water redistribution**Dimensionality** (8, 6)

Dimensionality Remarks 8: { Paved, Bldgs, EveTr, DecTr, Grass, BSoil, Water, one extra land cover type (currently NOT used)}

6: { Paved, Bldgs, EveTr, DecTr, Grass, BSoil}

SUEWS-related variables ToBSoil, ToBldgs, ToDecTr, ToEveTr, ToGrass, ToPaved, ToRunoff, ToSoilStore, ToWater

waterusemethod

Description Defines how external water use is calculated.

Dimensionality 0

Dimensionality Remarks Scalar

SUEWS-related variables WaterUseMethod

wetthresh

Description Depth of water which determines whether evaporation occurs from a partially wet or completely wet surface [mm].

Dimensionality (7,)

Dimensionality Remarks 7: { Paved, Bldgs, EveTr, DecTr, Grass, BSoil, Water}

SUEWS-related variables WetThreshold

wuprofa_24hr

Description Hourly profile values used in automatic irrigation.

Dimensionality (24, 2)

Dimensionality Remarks 24: hours of a day

2: {Weekday, Weekend}

SUEWS-related variables WaterUseProfAutoWD, WaterUseProfAutoWE

wuprofm_24hr

Description Hourly profile values used in manual irrigation.

Dimensionality (24, 2)

Dimensionality Remarks 24: hours of a day

2: {Weekday, Weekend}

SUEWS-related variables WaterUseProfManuWD, WaterUseProfManuWE

z

Description Measurement height [m].

Dimensionality 0

Dimensionality Remarks Scalar

SUEWS-related variables z

z0m_in

Description Roughness length for momentum [m]

Dimensionality 0

Dimensionality Remarks Scalar

SUEWS-related variables `z0`

`zdm_in`

Description Zero-plane displacement [m]

Dimensionality 0

Dimensionality Remarks Scalar

SUEWS-related variables `zd`

3.2.2 `df_forcing` variables

`RH`

Description Relative Humidity [%]

`Tair`

Description Air temperature [°C]

`U`

Description Wind speed [m s⁻¹] Height of the wind speed measurement (`z`) is needed in `SUEWS_SiteSelect.txt`.

`Wuh`

Description External water use [m³]

`fcld`

Description Cloud fraction [tenths]

`id`

Description Day of year [DOY]

`imin`

Description Minute [M]

`isec`

Description Second [S]

`it`

Description Hour [H]

`iy`

Description Year [YYYY]

`kdiff`

Description Diffuse radiation [W m⁻²] **Recommended in this version.** if `SOLWEIGUse = 1`

`kdir`

Description Direct radiation [W m⁻²] **Recommended in this version.** if `SOLWEIGUse = 1`

`kdown`

Description Incoming shortwave radiation [W m⁻²] Must be > 0 W m⁻².

`lai`

<code>ldown</code>	Description Observed leaf area index [$\text{m}^{-2} \text{m}^{-2}$]
	Description Incoming longwave radiation [W m^{-2}]
<code>pres</code>	Description Barometric pressure [kPa]
<code>qe</code>	Description Latent heat flux [W m^{-2}]
<code>qf</code>	Description Anthropogenic heat flux [W m^{-2}]
<code>qh</code>	Description Sensible heat flux [W m^{-2}]
<code>qn</code>	Description Net all-wave radiation [W m^{-2}] Required if <code>NetRadiationMethod = 0</code> .
<code>qs</code>	Description Storage heat flux [W m^{-2}]
<code>rain</code>	Description Rainfall [mm]
<code>snow</code>	Description Snow [mm] Required if <code>SnowUse = 1</code>
<code>wdir</code>	Description Wind direction [$^{\circ}$] Not available in this version.
<code>xsmc</code>	Description Observed soil moisture [$\text{m}^3 \text{m}^{-3}$] or [kg kg^{-1}]

3.2.3 df_output variables

AddWater

Description Additional water flow received from other grids [mm]

Group SUEWS

AlbBulk

Description Bulk albedo [-]

Group SUEWS

AlbDecTr

Description Albedo of deciduous trees [-]

Group DailyState

AlbEveTr

Description Albedo of evergreen trees [-]

Group DailyState

AlbGrass

Description Albedo of grass [-]

Group DailyState

AlbSnow

Description Snow albedo [-]

Group SUEWS

AlbSnow

Description Snow albedo [-]

Group DailyState

Azimuth

Description Solar azimuth angle [°]

Group SUEWS

DaysSR

Description Days since rain [days]

Group DailyState

DecidCap

Description Moisture storage capacity of deciduous trees [mm]

Group DailyState

DensSnow_BSoil

Description Snow density – bare soil surface [kg m⁻³]

Group DailyState

DensSnow_BSoil

Description Snow density - bare soil surface [kg m⁻³]

Group DailyState

DensSnow_BSoil

Description Snow density – bare soil surface [kg m⁻³]

Group snow

DensSnow_BSoil

Description Snow density - bare soil surface [kg m⁻³]

Group snow

DensSnow_Bldgs

Description Snow density – building surface [kg m⁻³]

Group snow

DensSnow_Bldgs

Description Snow density - building surface [kg m⁻³]

Group DailyState

DensSnow_Bldgs

Description Snow density – building surface [kg m⁻³]

Group DailyState

DensSnow_Bldgs

Description Snow density - building surface [kg m⁻³]

Group snow

DensSnow_DecTr

Description Snow density - deciduous surface [kg m⁻³]

Group DailyState

DensSnow_DecTr

Description Snow density - deciduous surface [kg m⁻³]

Group snow

DensSnow_DecTr

Description Snow density – deciduous surface [kg m⁻³]

Group snow

DensSnow_DecTr

Description Snow density – deciduous surface [kg m⁻³]

Group DailyState

DensSnow_EveTr

Description Snow density – evergreen surface [kg m⁻³]

Group snow

DensSnow_EveTr

Description Snow density – evergreen surface [kg m⁻³]

Group DailyState

DensSnow_EveTr

Description Snow density - evergreen surface [kg m⁻³]

Group snow

DensSnow_EveTr

Description Snow density - evergreen surface [kg m⁻³]

Group DailyState

DensSnow_Grass

Description Snow density – grass surface [kg m⁻³]

Group DailyState

DensSnow_Grass

Description Snow density - grass surface [kg m⁻³]

Group DailyState

DensSnow_Grass

Description Snow density - grass surface [kg m⁻³]

Group snow

DensSnow_Grass

Description Snow density – grass surface [kg m⁻³]

Group snow

DensSnow_Paved

Description Snow density – paved surface [kg m⁻³]

Group snow

DensSnow_Paved

Description Snow density - paved surface [kg m⁻³]

Group snow

DensSnow_Paved

Description Snow density – paved surface [kg m⁻³]

Group DailyState

DensSnow_Paved

Description Snow density - paved surface [kg m⁻³]

Group DailyState

DensSnow_Water

Description Snow density - water surface [kg m⁻³]

Group snow

DensSnow_Water

Description Snow density – water surface [kg m⁻³]

Group snow

DensSnow_Water

Description Snow density – water surface [kg m⁻³]

Group DailyState

DensSnow_Water

Description Snow density - water surface [kg m⁻³]

Group DailyState

Drainage

Description Drainage [mm]

Group SUEWS

Evap

Description Evaporation [mm]

Group SUEWS

Fc

Description CO2 flux [umol m⁻² s⁻¹] **Not available in this version.**

Group SUEWS

FcBuild

Description CO2 flux from buildings [umol m⁻² s⁻¹] **Not available in this version.**

Group SUEWS

FcMetab

Description CO2 flux from metabolism [umol m⁻² s⁻¹] **Not available in this version.**

Group SUEWS

FcPhoto

Description CO2 flux from photosynthesis [umol m⁻² s⁻¹] **Not available in this version.**

Group SUEWS

FcRespi

Description CO2 flux from respiration [umol m⁻² s⁻¹] **Not available in this version.**

Group SUEWS

FcTraff

Description CO2 flux from traffic [umol m⁻² s⁻¹] **Not available in this version.**

Group SUEWS

Fcld

Description Cloud fraction [-]

Group SUEWS

FlowCh

Description Additional flow into water body [mm]

Group SUEWS

GDD1_g

Description Growing degree days for leaf growth [°C]

Group DailyState

GDD2_s

Description Growing degree days for senescence [°C]

Group DailyState

GDD3_Tmin

Description Daily minimum temperature [°C]

Group DailyState

GDD4_Tmax

Description Daily maximum temperature [°C]

Group DailyState

GDD5_DLHrs

Description Day length [h]

Group DailyState

HDD1_h

Description Heating degree days [°C]

Group DailyState

HDD2_c

Description Cooling degree days [°C]

Group DailyState

HDD3_Tmean

Description Average daily air temperature [°C]

Group DailyState

HDD4_T5d

Description 5-day running-mean air temperature [°C]

Group DailyState

Irr

Description Irrigation [mm]

Group SUEWS

Kdown

Description Incoming shortwave radiation [W m^{-2}]

Group SUEWS

Kup

Description Outgoing shortwave radiation [W m^{-2}]

Group SUEWS

LAI

Description Leaf area index [$\text{m}^2 \text{m}^{-2}$]

Group SUEWS

LAI_DecTr

Description Leaf area index of deciduous trees [$\text{m}^2 \text{m}^{-2}$]

Group DailyState

LAI_EveTr

Description Leaf area index of evergreen trees [$\text{m}^2 \text{m}^{-2}$]

Group DailyState

LAI_Grass

Description Leaf area index of grass [$\text{m}^2 \text{m}^{-2}$]

Group DailyState

LAI1lumps

Description Leaf area index used in LUMPS (normalised 0-1) [-]

Group DailyState

Ldown

Description Incoming longwave radiation [W m^{-2}]

Group SUEWS

Lob

Description Obukhov length [m]

Group SUEWS

Lup

Description Outgoing longwave radiation [W m^{-2}]

Group SUEWS

MeltWStore

Description Meltwater store [mm]

Group SUEWS

MeltWater

Description Meltwater [mm]

Group SUEWS

MwStore_BSoil

Description Melt water store – bare soil surface [mm]

Group snow

MwStore_Bldgs

Description Melt water store – building surface [mm]

Group snow

MwStore_DecTr

Description Melt water store – deciduous surface [mm]

Group snow

MwStore_EveTr

Description Melt water store – evergreen surface [mm]

Group snow

MwStore_Grass

Description Melt water store – grass surface [mm]

Group snow

MwStore_Paved

Description Melt water store – paved surface [mm]

Group snow

MwStore_Water

Description Melt water store – water surface [mm]

Group snow

Mw_BSoil

Description Meltwater – bare soil surface [mm h⁻¹]

Group snow

Mw_Bldgs

Description Meltwater – building surface [mm h⁻¹]

Group snow

Mw_DecTr

Description Meltwater – deciduous surface [mm h⁻¹]

Group snow

Mw_EveTr

Description Meltwater – evergreen surface [mm h⁻¹]

Group snow

Mw_Grass

Description Meltwater – grass surface [mm h⁻¹ 1]

Group snow

Mw_Paved

Description Meltwater – paved surface [mm h⁻¹]

Group snow

Mw_Water

Description Meltwater – water surface [mm h⁻¹]

Group snow

NWtrState

Description Surface wetness state (for non-water surfaces) [mm]

Group SUEWS

P_day

Description Daily total precipitation [mm]

Group DailyState

Porosity

Description Porosity of deciduous trees [-]

Group DailyState

Q2

Description Air specific humidity at 2 m agl [g kg⁻¹]

Group SUEWS

QE

Description Latent heat flux (calculated using SUEWS) [W m^{-2}]

Group SUEWS

QElumps

Description Latent heat flux (calculated using LUMPS) [W m^{-2}]

Group SUEWS

QF

Description Anthropogenic heat flux [W m^{-2}]

Group SUEWS

QH

Description Sensible heat flux (calculated using SUEWS) [W m^{-2}]

Group SUEWS

QHlumps

Description Sensible heat flux (calculated using LUMPS) [W m^{-2}]

Group SUEWS

QHresis

Description Sensible heat flux (calculated using resistance method) [W m^{-2}]

Group SUEWS

QM

Description Snow-related heat exchange [W m^{-2}]

Group SUEWS

QMFreeze

Description Internal energy change [W m^{-2}]

Group SUEWS

QMRain

Description Heat released by rain on snow [W m^{-2}]

Group SUEWS

QN

Description Net all-wave radiation [W m^{-2}]

Group SUEWS

QNSnow

Description Net all-wave radiation for snow area [W m^{-2}]

Group SUEWS

QNSnowFr

Description Net all-wave radiation for snow-free area [W m^{-2}]

Group SUEWS

QS

Description Storage heat flux [W m^{-2}]

Group SUEWS

Qa_BSoil

Description Advective heat – bare soil surface [W m^{-2}]

Group snow

Qa_Bldgs

Description Advective heat – building surface [W m^{-2}]

Group snow

Qa_DecTr

Description Advective heat – deciduous surface [W m^{-2}]

Group snow

Qa_EveTr

Description Advective heat – evergreen surface [W m^{-2}]

Group snow

Qa_Grass

Description Advective heat – grass surface [W m^{-2}]

Group snow

Qa_Paved

Description Advective heat – paved surface [W m^{-2}]

Group snow

Qa_Water

Description Advective heat – water surface [W m^{-2}]

Group snow

QmFr_BSoil

Description Heat related to freezing of surface store – bare soil surface [W m^{-2}]

Group snow

QmFr_Bldgs

Description Heat related to freezing of surface store – building surface [W m^{-2}]

Group snow

QmFr_DecTr

Description Heat related to freezing of surface store – deciduous surface [W m^{-2}]

Group snow

QmFr_EveTr

Description Heat related to freezing of surface store – evergreen surface [W m^{-2}]

Group snow

QmFr_Grass

Description Heat related to freezing of surface store – grass surface [W m⁻²]

Group snow

QmFr_Paved

Description Heat related to freezing of surface store – paved surface [W m⁻²]

Group snow

QmFr_Water

Description Heat related to freezing of surface store – water [W m⁻²]

Group snow

Qm_BSoil

Description Snowmelt-related heat – bare soil surface [W m⁻²]

Group snow

Qm_Bldgs

Description Snowmelt-related heat – building surface [W m⁻²]

Group snow

Qm_DecTr

Description Snowmelt-related heat – deciduous surface [W m⁻²]

Group snow

Qm_EveTr

Description Snowmelt-related heat – evergreen surface [W m⁻²]

Group snow

Qm_Grass

Description Snowmelt-related heat – grass surface [W m⁻²]

Group snow

Qm_Paved

Description Snowmelt-related heat – paved surface [W m⁻²]

Group snow

Qm_Water

Description Snowmelt-related heat – water surface [W m⁻²]

Group snow

RA

Description Aerodynamic resistance [s m⁻¹]

Group SUEWS

RO

Description Runoff [mm]

Group SUEWS

ROImp

Description Above ground runoff over impervious surfaces [mm]

Group SUEWS

ROPipe

Description Runoff to pipes [mm]

Group SUEWS

ROSoil

Description Runoff to soil (sub-surface) [mm]

Group SUEWS

ROVeg

Description Above ground runoff over vegetated surfaces [mm]

Group SUEWS

ROWater

Description Runoff for water body [mm]

Group SUEWS

RS

Description Surface resistance [s m^{-1}]

Group SUEWS

Rain

Description Rain [mm]

Group SUEWS

RainSn_BSoil

Description Rain on snow – bare soil surface [mm]

Group snow

RainSn_Bldgs

Description Rain on snow – building surface [mm]

Group snow

RainSn_DecTr

Description Rain on snow – deciduous surface [mm]

Group snow

RainSn_EveTr

Description Rain on snow – evergreen surface [mm]

Group snow

RainSn_Grass

Description Rain on snow – grass surface [mm]

Group snow

RainSn_Paved

Description Rain on snow – paved surface [mm]

Group snow

RainSn_Water

Description Rain on snow – water surface [mm]

Group snow

SMD

Description Soil moisture deficit [mm]

Group SUEWS

SMDBSoil

Description Soil moisture deficit for bare soil surface [mm]

Group SUEWS

SMDBldgs

Description Soil moisture deficit for building surface [mm]

Group SUEWS

SMDDecTr

Description Soil moisture deficit for deciduous surface [mm]

Group SUEWS

SMDEveTr

Description Soil moisture deficit for evergreen surface [mm]

Group SUEWS

SMDGrass

Description Soil moisture deficit for grass surface [mm]

Group SUEWS

SMDPaved

Description Soil moisture deficit for paved surface [mm]

Group SUEWS

SWE

Description Snow water equivalent [mm]

Group SUEWS

SWE_BSoil

Description Snow water equivalent – bare soil surface [mm]

Group snow

SWE_Bldgs

Description Snow water equivalent – building surface [mm]

Group snow

SWE_DecTr

Description Snow water equivalent – deciduous surface [mm]

Group snow

SWE_EveTr

Description Snow water equivalent – evergreen surface [mm]

Group snow

SWE_Grass

Description Snow water equivalent – grass surface [mm]

Group snow

SWE_Paved

Description Snow water equivalent – paved surface [mm]

Group snow

SWE_Water

Description Snow water equivalent – water surface [mm]

Group snow

Sd_BSoil

Description Snow depth – bare soil surface [mm]

Group snow

Sd_Bldgs

Description Snow depth – building surface [mm]

Group snow

Sd_DecTr

Description Snow depth – deciduous surface [mm]

Group snow

Sd_EveTr

Description Snow depth – evergreen surface [mm]

Group snow

Sd_Grass

Description Snow depth – grass surface [mm]

Group snow

Sd_Paved

Description Snow depth – paved surface [mm]

Group snow

Sd_Water

Description Snow depth – water surface [mm]

Group snow

SnowCh

Description Change in snow pack [mm]

Group SUEWS

SnowRBldgs

Description Snow removed from building surface [mm]

Group SUEWS

SnowRPaved

Description Snow removed from paved surface [mm]

Group SUEWS

StBSoil

Description Surface wetness state for bare soil surface [mm]

Group SUEWS

StBldgs

Description Surface wetness state for building surface [mm]

Group SUEWS

StDecTr

Description Surface wetness state for deciduous tree surface [mm]

Group SUEWS

StEveTr

Description Surface wetness state for evergreen tree surface [mm]

Group SUEWS

StGrass

Description Surface wetness state for grass surface [mm]

Group SUEWS

StPaved

Description Surface wetness state for paved surface [mm]

Group SUEWS

StWater

Description Surface wetness state for water surface [mm]

Group SUEWS

State

Description Surface wetness state [mm]

Group SUEWS

SurfCh

Description Change in surface moisture store [mm]

	Group SUEWS
T2	Description Air temperature at 2 m agl [°C] Group SUEWS
TotCh	Description Change in surface and soil moisture stores [mm] Group SUEWS
Ts	Description Skin temperature [°C] Group SUEWS
Tsnow_BSoil	Description Snow surface temperature – bare soil surface [°C] Group snow
Tsnow_Bldgs	Description Snow surface temperature – building surface [°C] Group snow
Tsnow_DecTr	Description Snow surface temperature – deciduous surface [°C] Group snow
Tsnow_EveTr	Description Snow surface temperature – evergreen surface [°C] Group snow
Tsnow_Grass	Description Snow surface temperature – grass surface [°C] Group snow
Tsnow_Paved	Description Snow surface temperature – paved surface [°C] Group snow
Tsnow_Water	Description Snow surface temperature – water surface [°C] Group snow
Tsurf	Description Bulk surface temperature [°C] Group SUEWS
U10	Description Wind speed at 10 m agl [m s ⁻¹]

Group SUEWS

WUDecTr

Description Water use for irrigation of deciduous trees [mm]

Group SUEWS

WUEveTr

Description Water use for irrigation of evergreen trees [mm]

Group SUEWS

WUGrass

Description Water use for irrigation of grass [mm]

Group SUEWS

WUInt

Description Internal water use [mm]

Group SUEWS

WU_DecTr1

Description Total water use for deciduous trees [mm]

Group DailyState

WU_DecTr2

Description Automatic water use for deciduous trees [mm]

Group DailyState

WU_DecTr3

Description Manual water use for deciduous trees [mm]

Group DailyState

WU_EveTr1

Description Total water use for evergreen trees [mm]

Group DailyState

WU_EveTr2

Description Automatic water use for evergreen trees [mm]

Group DailyState

WU_EveTr3

Description Manual water use for evergreen trees [mm]

Group DailyState

WU_Grass1

Description Total water use for grass [mm]

Group DailyState

WU_Grass2

Description Automatic water use for grass [mm]

Group DailyState

WU_Grass3

Description Manual water use for grass [mm]

Group DailyState

Zenith

Description Solar zenith angle [°]

Group SUEWS

a1

Description OHM coefficient a1 - [-]

Group DailyState

a2

Description OHM coefficient a2 [$\text{W m}^{-2} \text{h}^{-1}$]

Group DailyState

a3

Description OHM coefficient a3 - [W m^{-2}]

Group DailyState

deltaLAI

Description Change in leaf area index (normalised 0-1) [-]

Group DailyState

frMelt_BSoil

Description Amount of freezing melt water – bare soil surface [mm]

Group snow

frMelt_Bldgs

Description Amount of freezing melt water – building surface [mm]

Group snow

frMelt_DecTr

Description Amount of freezing melt water – deciduous surface [mm]

Group snow

frMelt_EveTr

Description Amount of freezing melt water – evergreen surface [mm]

Group snow

frMelt_Grass

Description Amount of freezing melt water – grass surface [mm]

Group snow

frMelt_Paved

Description Amount of freezing melt water – paved surface [mm]

Group snow

frMelt_Water

Description Amount of freezing melt water – water surface [mm]

Group snow

fr_Bldgs

Description Fraction of snow – building surface [-]

Group snow

fr_DecTr

Description Fraction of snow – deciduous surface [-]

Group snow

fr_EveTr

Description Fraction of snow – evergreen surface [-]

Group snow

fr_Grass

Description Fraction of snow – grass surface [-]

Group snow

fr_Paved

Description Fraction of snow – paved surface [-]

Group snow

kup_BSoilSnow

Description Reflected shortwave radiation – bare soil surface [W m^{-2}]

Group snow

kup_BldgsSnow

Description Reflected shortwave radiation – building surface [W m^{-2}]

Group snow

kup_DecTrSnow

Description Reflected shortwave radiation – deciduous surface [W m^{-2}]

Group snow

kup_EveTrSnow

Description Reflected shortwave radiation – evergreen surface [W m^{-2}]

Group snow

kup_GrassSnow

Description Reflected shortwave radiation – grass surface [W m^{-2}]

Group snow

kup_PavedSnow

Description Reflected shortwave radiation – paved surface [W m^{-2}]

Group snow

kup_WaterSnow

Description Reflected shortwave radiation – water surface [W m^{-2}]

Group snow

z0m

Description Roughness length for momentum [m]

Group SUEWS

zdm

Description Zero-plane displacement height [m]

Group SUEWS

4.1 Version 2019.1.1 (preview release, 01 Jan 2019)

- **New**
 1. Slimmed the output groups by excluding unsupported **ESTM** results
 2. SuPy documentation
 - Key IO data structures documented:
 - *df_output variables* (GH9)
 - *df_state variables* (GH8)
 - *df_forcing variables* (GH7)
 - Tutorial of parallel SuPy simulations for impact studies
- **Improvement**
 1. Improved calculation of OHM-related radiation terms
- **Changes**

None.
- **Fix**

None
- **Known issue**

None

4.2 Version 2018.12.15 (internal test release in December 2018)

- **New**

1. Preview release of SuPy based on the computation kernel of SUEWS 2018b

- **Improvement**

1. Improved calculation of OHM-related radiation terms

- **Changes**

None.

- **Fix**

None

- **Known issue**

1. The heat storage modules AnOHM and ESTM are not supported yet.

4.3 Version 2019.2.8 (under development)

This is a release that fixes recent bugs found in SUEWS that may lead to abnormal simulation results of storage heat flux, in particular when `SnowUse` is enabled (i.e., `snowuse=1`).

- **New**

None.

- **Improvement**

Improved the performance in loading initial model state from a large number of grids (>1k)

- **Changes**

Updated `SampleRun` dataset by: 1. setting surface fractions (`sfr`) to a more realistic value based on London KCL case; 2. enabling snow module (`snowuse=1`).

- **Fix**

1. Fixed a bug in the calculation of storage heat flux.
2. Fixed a bug in loading `popdens` for calculating anthropogenic heat flux.

- **Known issue**

None

A

a1
command line option, 87

a2
command line option, 87

a3
command line option, 87

AddWater
command line option, 70

aerodynamicresistancemethod
command line option, 45

ah_min
command line option, 45

ah_slope_cooling
command line option, 45

ah_slope_heating
command line option, 45

ahprof_24hr
command line option, 45

alb
command line option, 46

AlbBulk
command line option, 70

AlbDecTr
command line option, 70

albdectr_id
command line option, 46

AlbEveTr
command line option, 70

albevetr_id
command line option, 46

AlbGrass
command line option, 71

albgrass_id
command line option, 46

albmax_dectr
command line option, 46

albmax_evetr
command line option, 46

albmax_grass
command line option, 46

albmin_dectr
command line option, 46

albmin_evetr
command line option, 47

albmin_grass
command line option, 47

AlbSnow
command line option, 71

alpha_bioco2
command line option, 47

alpha_enh_bioco2
command line option, 47

alt
command line option, 47

Azimuth
command line option, 71

B

baset
command line option, 47

basete
command line option, 47

basethdd
command line option, 48

beta_bioco2
command line option, 48

beta_enh_bioco2
command line option, 48

bldgh
command line option, 48

C

capmax_dec
command line option, 48

capmin_dec
command line option, 48

chanohm

- command line option, 48
- command line option
 - a1, 87
 - a2, 87
 - a3, 87
 - AddWater, 70
 - aerodynamicresistancemethod, 45
 - ah_min, 45
 - ah_slope_cooling, 45
 - ah_slope_heating, 45
 - ahprof_24hr, 45
 - alb, 46
 - AlbBulk, 70
 - AlbDecTr, 70
 - albdectr_id, 46
 - AlbEveTr, 70
 - albevetr_id, 46
 - AlbGrass, 71
 - albgrass_id, 46
 - albmax_dectr, 46
 - albmax_evetr, 46
 - albmax_grass, 46
 - albmin_dectr, 46
 - albmin_evetr, 47
 - albmin_grass, 47
 - AlbSnow, 71
 - alpha_bioco2, 47
 - alpha_enh_bioco2, 47
 - alt, 47
 - Azimuth, 71
 - baset, 47
 - basete, 47
 - basethdd, 48
 - beta_bioco2, 48
 - beta_enh_bioco2, 48
 - bldgh, 48
 - capmax_dec, 48
 - capmin_dec, 48
 - chanohm, 48
 - cpanohm, 49
 - crwmax, 49
 - crwmin, 49
 - DaysSR, 71
 - daywat, 49
 - daywatper, 49
 - DecidCap, 71
 - decidcap_id, 49
 - dectreeh, 49
 - deltaLAI, 87
 - DensSnow_Bldgs, 71, 72
 - DensSnow_BSoil, 71
 - DensSnow_DecTr, 72
 - DensSnow_EveTr, 72
 - DensSnow_Grass, 72, 73
 - DensSnow_Paved, 73
 - DensSnow_Water, 73
 - diagnose, 50
 - diagqn, 50
 - diagqs, 50
 - Drainage, 73
 - drainrt, 50
 - ef_umolco2perj, 50
 - emis, 50
 - emissionsmethod, 50
 - enddls, 51
 - enef_v_jkm, 51
 - Evap, 73
 - evapmethod, 51
 - evetreeh, 51
 - faibldg, 51
 - faidectree, 51
 - faievetree, 51
 - faut, 52
 - Fc, 74
 - FcBuild, 74
 - fcef_v_kgkm, 52
 - Fcld, 74
 - fcl, 69
 - FcMetab, 74
 - FcPhoto, 74
 - FcRespi, 74
 - FcTraff, 74
 - FlowCh, 74
 - flowchange, 52
 - fr_Bldgs, 88
 - fr_DecTr, 88
 - fr_EveTr, 88
 - fr_Grass, 88
 - fr_Paved, 88
 - frfossilfuel_heat, 52
 - frfossilfuel_nonheat, 52
 - frMelt_Bldgs, 87
 - frMelt_BSoil, 87
 - frMelt_DecTr, 87
 - frMelt_EveTr, 87
 - frMelt_Grass, 87
 - frMelt_Paved, 87
 - frMelt_Water, 88
 - g1, 52
 - g2, 52
 - g3, 53
 - g4, 53
 - g5, 53
 - g6, 53
 - GDD1_g, 74
 - GDD2_s, 74
 - GDD3_Tmin, 74
 - GDD4_Tmax, 74

GDD5_DLHrs, 75
 gddfull, 53
 gsmodel, 53
 HDD1_h, 75
 HDD2_c, 75
 HDD3_Tmean, 75
 HDD4_T5d, 75
 humactivity_24hr, 53
 id, 69
 ie_a, 54
 ie_end, 54
 ie_m, 54
 ie_start, 54
 imin, 69
 internalwateruse_h, 54
 Irr, 75
 irrfractionif, 54
 irrfractiondecid, 54
 irrfractiongrass, 55
 isec, 69
 it, 69
 iy, 69
 kdiff, 69
 kdir, 69
 Kdown, 75
 kdown, 69
 kkanohm, 55
 kmax, 55
 Kup, 75
 kup_BldgsSnow, 88
 kup_BSoilSnow, 88
 kup_DecTrSnow, 88
 kup_EveTrSnow, 88
 kup_GrassSnow, 88
 kup_PavedSnow, 88
 kup_WaterSnow, 89
 LAI, 75
 lai, 69
 LAI_DecTr, 75
 LAI_EveTr, 75
 LAI_Grass, 75
 lai_id, 55
 laicalcyes, 55
 LAlumps, 76
 laimax, 55
 laimin, 55
 laipower, 56
 laitype, 56
 lat, 56
 Ldown, 76
 ldown, 70
 lng, 56
 Lob, 76
 Lup, 76
 maxconductance, 56
 maxqfmetab, 56
 MeltWater, 76
 MeltWStore, 76
 min_res_bioco2, 56
 minqfmetab, 57
 Mw_Bldgs, 77
 Mw_BSoil, 77
 Mw_DecTr, 77
 Mw_EveTr, 77
 Mw_Grass, 77
 Mw_Paved, 77
 Mw_Water, 77
 MwStore_Bldgs, 76
 MwStore_BSoil, 76
 MwStore_DecTr, 76
 MwStore_EveTr, 76
 MwStore_Grass, 76
 MwStore_Paved, 76
 MwStore_Water, 77
 narp_emis_snow, 57
 narp_trans_site, 57
 netradiationmethod, 57
 NWtrState, 77
 ohm_coef, 57
 ohm_threshsw, 57
 ohm_threshwd, 57
 ohmincqf, 58
 P_day, 77
 pipecapacity, 58
 popdensdaytime, 58
 popdensnighttime, 58
 popprof_24hr, 58
 pormax_dec, 58
 pormin_dec, 59
 Porosity, 77
 porosity_id, 59
 preciplimit, 59
 preciplimitalb, 59
 pres, 70
 Q2, 77
 Qa_Bldgs, 79
 Qa_BSoil, 79
 Qa_DecTr, 79
 Qa_EveTr, 79
 Qa_Grass, 79
 Qa_Paved, 79
 Qa_Water, 79
 QE, 78
 qe, 70
 QElumps, 78
 QF, 78
 qf, 70
 qf0_beu, 59

qf_a, 59
qf_b, 59
qf_c, 60
QH, 78
qh, 70
QHlumps, 78
QHresis, 78
QM, 78
Qm_Bldgs, 80
Qm_BSoil, 80
Qm_DecTr, 80
Qm_EveTr, 80
Qm_Grass, 80
Qm_Paved, 80
Qm_Water, 80
QmFr_Bldgs, 79
QmFr_BSoil, 79
QmFr_DecTr, 79
QmFr_EveTr, 79
QmFr_Grass, 80
QmFr_Paved, 80
QmFr_Water, 80
QMFreeze, 78
QMRain, 78
QN, 78
qn, 70
QNSnow, 78
QNSnowFr, 78
QS, 79
qs, 70
RA, 80
radmeltfact, 60
Rain, 81
rain, 70
raincover, 60
rainmaxres, 60
RainSn_Bldgs, 81
RainSn_BSoil, 81
RainSn_DecTr, 81
RainSn_EveTr, 81
RainSn_Grass, 81
RainSn_Paved, 82
RainSn_Water, 82
resp_a, 60
resp_b, 60
RH, 69
RO, 80
ROImp, 81
ROPipe, 81
ROSoil, 81
roughlenheatmethod, 60
roughlenmommommethod, 60
ROVeg, 81
ROWater, 81
RS, 81
runofftowater, 61
s1, 61
s2, 61
sathydraulicconduct, 61
Sd_Bldgs, 83
Sd_BSoil, 83
Sd_DecTr, 83
Sd_EveTr, 83
Sd_Grass, 83
Sd_Paved, 83
Sd_Water, 83
sddfull, 61
sfr, 61
SMD, 82
SMDBldgs, 82
SMDBSoil, 82
SMDDecTr, 82
SMDEveTr, 82
SMDGrass, 82
smdmethod, 61
SMDPaved, 82
snow, 70
snowalb, 62
snowalbmax, 62
snowalbmin, 62
SnowCh, 84
snowdens, 62
snowdensmax, 62
snowdensmin, 62
snowfrac, 62
snowlimbldg, 63
snowlimpaved, 63
snowpack, 63
snowpacklimit, 63
snowprof_24hr, 63
SnowRBldgs, 84
SnowRPaved, 84
snowuse, 63
snowwater, 64
soildepth, 64
soilstore_id, 64
soilstorecap, 64
stabilitymethod, 64
startdls, 64
State, 84
state_id, 64
statelimit, 65
StBldgs, 84
StBSoil, 84
StDecTr, 84
StEveTr, 84
StGrass, 84
storageheatmethod, 65

storedrainprm, 65
 StPaved, 84
 StWater, 84
 surfacearea, 65
 SurfCh, 84
 SWE, 82
 SWE_Bldgs, 82
 SWE_BSoil, 82
 SWE_DecTr, 83
 SWE_EveTr, 83
 SWE_Grass, 83
 SWE_Paved, 83
 SWE_Water, 83
 T2, 85
 t_critic_cooling, 65
 t_critic_heating, 65
 Tair, 69
 tau_a, 65
 tau_f, 66
 tau_r, 66
 tempmeltfact, 66
 th, 66
 theta_bioco2, 66
 timezone, 66
 tl, 66
 TotCh, 85
 trafficrate, 67
 trafficunits, 67
 traffprof_24hr, 67
 Ts, 85
 Tsnow_Bldgs, 85
 Tsnow_BSoil, 85
 Tsnow_DecTr, 85
 Tsnow_EveTr, 85
 Tsnow_Grass, 85
 Tsnow_Paved, 85
 Tsnow_Water, 85
 tstep, 67
 Tsurf, 85
 U, 69
 U10, 85
 veg_type, 67
 waterdist, 67
 waterusemethod, 68
 wdir, 70
 wetthresh, 68
 WU_DecTr1, 86
 WU_DecTr2, 86
 WU_DecTr3, 86
 WU_EveTr1, 86
 WU_EveTr2, 86
 WU_EveTr3, 86
 WU_Grass1, 86
 WU_Grass2, 86
 WU_Grass3, 87
 WUDecTr, 86
 WUEveTr, 86
 WUGrass, 86
 Wuh, 69
 WUInt, 86
 wuprofa_24hr, 68
 wuprofm_24hr, 68
 xsmd, 70
 z, 68
 z0m, 89
 z0m_in, 68
 zdm, 89
 zdm_in, 69
 Zenith, 87
 cpanohm
 command line option, 49
 crwmax
 command line option, 49
 crwmin
 command line option, 49
D
 DaysSR
 command line option, 71
 daywat
 command line option, 49
 daywatper
 command line option, 49
 DecidCap
 command line option, 71
 decidcap_id
 command line option, 49
 dectreeh
 command line option, 49
 deltaLAI
 command line option, 87
 DensSnow_Bldgs
 command line option, 71, 72
 DensSnow_BSoil
 command line option, 71
 DensSnow_DecTr
 command line option, 72
 DensSnow_EveTr
 command line option, 72
 DensSnow_Grass
 command line option, 72, 73
 DensSnow_Paved
 command line option, 73
 DensSnow_Water
 command line option, 73
 diagnose
 command line option, 50
 diagqn

- command line option, 50
- diagqs
 - command line option, 50
- Drainage
 - command line option, 73
- drainrt
 - command line option, 50

E

- ef_umolco2perj
 - command line option, 50
- emis
 - command line option, 50
- emissionsmethod
 - command line option, 50
- enddls
 - command line option, 51
- enef_v_jkm
 - command line option, 51
- Evap
 - command line option, 73
- evapmethod
 - command line option, 51
- evetreeh
 - command line option, 51

F

- faibldg
 - command line option, 51
- faidectree
 - command line option, 51
- faievetree
 - command line option, 51
- faut
 - command line option, 52
- Fc
 - command line option, 74
- FcBuild
 - command line option, 74
- fcef_v_kgkm
 - command line option, 52
- Fcld
 - command line option, 74
- fcld
 - command line option, 69
- FcMetab
 - command line option, 74
- FcPhoto
 - command line option, 74
- FcRespi
 - command line option, 74
- FcTraff
 - command line option, 74
- FlowCh

- command line option, 74
- flowchange
 - command line option, 52
- fr_Bldgs
 - command line option, 88
- fr_DecTr
 - command line option, 88
- fr_EveTr
 - command line option, 88
- fr_Grass
 - command line option, 88
- fr_Paved
 - command line option, 88
- frfossilfuel_heat
 - command line option, 52
- frfossilfuel_nonheat
 - command line option, 52
- frMelt_Bldgs
 - command line option, 87
- frMelt_BSoil
 - command line option, 87
- frMelt_DecTr
 - command line option, 87
- frMelt_EveTr
 - command line option, 87
- frMelt_Grass
 - command line option, 87
- frMelt_Paved
 - command line option, 87
- frMelt_Water
 - command line option, 88

G

- g1
 - command line option, 52
- g2
 - command line option, 52
- g3
 - command line option, 53
- g4
 - command line option, 53
- g5
 - command line option, 53
- g6
 - command line option, 53
- GDD1_g
 - command line option, 74
- GDD2_s
 - command line option, 74
- GDD3_Tmin
 - command line option, 74
- GDD4_Tmax
 - command line option, 74
- GDD5_DLHrs

command line option, 75
 gddfull
 command line option, 53
 gsmodel
 command line option, 53

H

HDD1_h
 command line option, 75
 HDD2_c
 command line option, 75
 HDD3_Tmean
 command line option, 75
 HDD4_T5d
 command line option, 75
 humactivity_24hr
 command line option, 53

I

id
 command line option, 69
 ie_a
 command line option, 54
 ie_end
 command line option, 54
 ie_m
 command line option, 54
 ie_start
 command line option, 54
 imin
 command line option, 69
 init_supy() (in module supy), 43
 internalwateruse_h
 command line option, 54
 Irr
 command line option, 75
 irrfraconif
 command line option, 54
 irrfra decid
 command line option, 54
 irrfra grass
 command line option, 55
 isec
 command line option, 69
 it
 command line option, 69
 iy
 command line option, 69

K

kdiff
 command line option, 69
 kdir
 command line option, 69

Kdown
 command line option, 75
 kdown
 command line option, 69
 kkanohm
 command line option, 55
 kmax
 command line option, 55
 Kup
 command line option, 75
 kup_BldgsSnow
 command line option, 88
 kup_BSoilSnow
 command line option, 88
 kup_DecTrSnow
 command line option, 88
 kup_EveTrSnow
 command line option, 88
 kup_GrassSnow
 command line option, 88
 kup_PavedSnow
 command line option, 88
 kup_WaterSnow
 command line option, 89

L

LAI
 command line option, 75
 lai
 command line option, 69
 LAI_DecTr
 command line option, 75
 LAI_EveTr
 command line option, 75
 LAI_Grass
 command line option, 75
 lai_id
 command line option, 55
 laicalcyes
 command line option, 55
 LAIlumps
 command line option, 76
 laimax
 command line option, 55
 laimin
 command line option, 55
 laipower
 command line option, 56
 laitype
 command line option, 56
 lat
 command line option, 56
 Ldown
 command line option, 76

ldown
 command line option, 70
 lng
 command line option, 56
 load_forcing_grid() (in module supy), 43
 load_SampleData() (in module supy), 44
 Lob
 command line option, 76
 Lup
 command line option, 76

M

maxconductance
 command line option, 56
 maxqfmetab
 command line option, 56
 MeltWater
 command line option, 76
 MeltWStore
 command line option, 76
 min_res_bioco2
 command line option, 56
 minqfmetab
 command line option, 57
 Mw_Bldgs
 command line option, 77
 Mw_BSoil
 command line option, 77
 Mw_DecTr
 command line option, 77
 Mw_EveTr
 command line option, 77
 Mw_Grass
 command line option, 77
 Mw_Paved
 command line option, 77
 Mw_Water
 command line option, 77
 MwStore_Bldgs
 command line option, 76
 MwStore_BSoil
 command line option, 76
 MwStore_DecTr
 command line option, 76
 MwStore_EveTr
 command line option, 76
 MwStore_Grass
 command line option, 76
 MwStore_Paved
 command line option, 76
 MwStore_Water
 command line option, 77

N

narp_emis_snow
 command line option, 57
 narp_trans_site
 command line option, 57
 netradiationmethod
 command line option, 57
 NWtrState
 command line option, 77

O

ohm_coef
 command line option, 57
 ohm_threshsw
 command line option, 57
 ohm_threshwd
 command line option, 57
 ohmincqf
 command line option, 58

P

P_day
 command line option, 77
 pipecapacity
 command line option, 58
 popdensdaytime
 command line option, 58
 popdensnighttime
 command line option, 58
 popprof_24hr
 command line option, 58
 pormax_dec
 command line option, 58
 pormin_dec
 command line option, 59
 Porosity
 command line option, 77
 porosity_id
 command line option, 59
 precliplimit
 command line option, 59
 precliplimitlb
 command line option, 59
 pres
 command line option, 70

Q

Q2
 command line option, 77
 Qa_Bldgs
 command line option, 79
 Qa_BSoil
 command line option, 79

- Qa_DecTr
 command line option, 79
- Qa_EveTr
 command line option, 79
- Qa_Grass
 command line option, 79
- Qa_Paved
 command line option, 79
- Qa_Water
 command line option, 79
- QE
 command line option, 78
- qe
 command line option, 70
- QElumps
 command line option, 78
- QF
 command line option, 78
- qf
 command line option, 70
- qf0_beu
 command line option, 59
- qf_a
 command line option, 59
- qf_b
 command line option, 59
- qf_c
 command line option, 60
- QH
 command line option, 78
- qh
 command line option, 70
- QHlumps
 command line option, 78
- QHresis
 command line option, 78
- QM
 command line option, 78
- Qm_Bldgs
 command line option, 80
- Qm_BSoil
 command line option, 80
- Qm_DecTr
 command line option, 80
- Qm_EveTr
 command line option, 80
- Qm_Grass
 command line option, 80
- Qm_Paved
 command line option, 80
- Qm_Water
 command line option, 80
- QmFr_Bldgs
 command line option, 79
- QmFr_BSoil
 command line option, 79
- QmFr_DecTr
 command line option, 79
- QmFr_EveTr
 command line option, 79
- QmFr_Grass
 command line option, 80
- QmFr_Paved
 command line option, 80
- QmFr_Water
 command line option, 80
- QMFreeze
 command line option, 78
- QMRain
 command line option, 78
- QN
 command line option, 78
- qn
 command line option, 70
- QNSnow
 command line option, 78
- QNSnowFr
 command line option, 78
- QS
 command line option, 79
- qs
 command line option, 70
- ## R
- RA
 command line option, 80
- radmeltfact
 command line option, 60
- Rain
 command line option, 81
- rain
 command line option, 70
- raincover
 command line option, 60
- rainmaxres
 command line option, 60
- RainSn_Bldgs
 command line option, 81
- RainSn_BSoil
 command line option, 81
- RainSn_DecTr
 command line option, 81
- RainSn_EveTr
 command line option, 81
- RainSn_Grass
 command line option, 81
- RainSn_Paved
 command line option, 82

- RainSn_Water
 - command line option, 82
- resp_a
 - command line option, 60
- resp_b
 - command line option, 60
- RH
 - command line option, 69
- RO
 - command line option, 80
- ROImp
 - command line option, 81
- ROPipe
 - command line option, 81
- ROSoil
 - command line option, 81
- roughlenheatmethod
 - command line option, 60
- roughlenmommethode
 - command line option, 60
- ROVeg
 - command line option, 81
- ROWater
 - command line option, 81
- RS
 - command line option, 81
- run_supy() (in module supy), 44
- runofftewater
 - command line option, 61
- S**
- s1
 - command line option, 61
- s2
 - command line option, 61
- sathdraulicconduct
 - command line option, 61
- Sd_Bldgs
 - command line option, 83
- Sd_BSoil
 - command line option, 83
- Sd_DecTr
 - command line option, 83
- Sd_EveTr
 - command line option, 83
- Sd_Grass
 - command line option, 83
- Sd_Paved
 - command line option, 83
- Sd_Water
 - command line option, 83
- sddfll
 - command line option, 61
- sfr
 - command line option, 61
- SMD
 - command line option, 82
- SMDBldgs
 - command line option, 82
- SMDBSoil
 - command line option, 82
- SMDDecTr
 - command line option, 82
- SMDEveTr
 - command line option, 82
- SMDGrass
 - command line option, 82
- smdmethod
 - command line option, 61
- SMDPaved
 - command line option, 82
- snow
 - command line option, 70
- snowalb
 - command line option, 62
- snowalbmax
 - command line option, 62
- snowalbmin
 - command line option, 62
- SnowCh
 - command line option, 84
- snowdens
 - command line option, 62
- snowdensmax
 - command line option, 62
- snowdensmin
 - command line option, 62
- snowfrac
 - command line option, 62
- snowlimbldg
 - command line option, 63
- snowlimpaved
 - command line option, 63
- snowpack
 - command line option, 63
- snowpacklimit
 - command line option, 63
- snowprof_24hr
 - command line option, 63
- SnowRBldgs
 - command line option, 84
- SnowRPaved
 - command line option, 84
- snowuse
 - command line option, 63
- snowwater
 - command line option, 64
- soildepth

command line option, 64
 soilstore_id
 command line option, 64
 soilstorecap
 command line option, 64
 stabilitymethod
 command line option, 64
 startdls
 command line option, 64
 State
 command line option, 84
 state_id
 command line option, 64
 statelimit
 command line option, 65
 StBldgs
 command line option, 84
 StBSoil
 command line option, 84
 StDecTr
 command line option, 84
 StEveTr
 command line option, 84
 StGrass
 command line option, 84
 storageheatmethod
 command line option, 65
 storedrainprm
 command line option, 65
 StPaved
 command line option, 84
 StWater
 command line option, 84
 surfacearea
 command line option, 65
 SurfCh
 command line option, 84
 SWE
 command line option, 82
 SWE_Bldgs
 command line option, 82
 SWE_BSoil
 command line option, 82
 SWE_DecTr
 command line option, 83
 SWE_EveTr
 command line option, 83
 SWE_Grass
 command line option, 83
 SWE_Paved
 command line option, 83
 SWE_Water
 command line option, 83

T

T2
 command line option, 85
 t_critic_cooling
 command line option, 65
 t_critic_heating
 command line option, 65
 Tair
 command line option, 69
 tau_a
 command line option, 65
 tau_f
 command line option, 66
 tau_r
 command line option, 66
 tempmelfact
 command line option, 66
 th
 command line option, 66
 theta_bioco2
 command line option, 66
 timezone
 command line option, 66
 tl
 command line option, 66
 TotCh
 command line option, 85
 trafficrate
 command line option, 67
 trafficunits
 command line option, 67
 traffprof_24hr
 command line option, 67
 Ts
 command line option, 85
 Tsnow_Bldgs
 command line option, 85
 Tsnow_BSoil
 command line option, 85
 Tsnow_DecTr
 command line option, 85
 Tsnow_EveTr
 command line option, 85
 Tsnow_Grass
 command line option, 85
 Tsnow_Paved
 command line option, 85
 Tsnow_Water
 command line option, 85
 timestep
 command line option, 67
 Tsurf
 command line option, 85

U

- U
command line option, 69
- U10
command line option, 85

V

- veg_type
command line option, 67

W

- waterdist
command line option, 67
- waterusemethod
command line option, 68
- wdir
command line option, 70
- wetthresh
command line option, 68
- WU_DecTr1
command line option, 86
- WU_DecTr2
command line option, 86
- WU_DecTr3
command line option, 86
- WU_EveTr1
command line option, 86
- WU_EveTr2
command line option, 86
- WU_EveTr3
command line option, 86
- WU_Grass1
command line option, 86
- WU_Grass2
command line option, 86
- WU_Grass3
command line option, 87
- WUDecTr
command line option, 86
- WUEveTr
command line option, 86
- WUGrass
command line option, 86
- Wuh
command line option, 69
- WUInt
command line option, 86
- wuprofa_24hr
command line option, 68
- wuprofm_24hr
command line option, 68

X

- xsmc

- command line option, 70

Z

- z
command line option, 68
- z0m
command line option, 89
- z0m_in
command line option, 68
- zdm
command line option, 89
- zdm_in
command line option, 69
- Zenith
command line option, 87